

VITAMIN D AND ITS PHYTO-DERIVED MIMETICS AMELIORATE VERTIGO AND ASSOCIATED SYSTEMIC DISORDERS:

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ABSTRACT

Four case reports are presented which may underline the useful role of vitamin D3 receptor agonists/mimetics and non-addictive flumazenil-insensitive GABAergic enhancers in the management of central and peripheral vertigo.

- Turmeric, lemon-ginger and black pepper teas;
- chamomile, strawberry and green teas;
- rosemary, chamomile teas + tadalafil;
- turmeric, strawberry teas + vitamin D3

were administered to 1-4 patients respectively.

Their effect on vertigo/dizziness, infection incidence, MMSE, and other selected neuro-cardio-metabolic parameters were assessed at 3 and 6 months. Although all the treatments had noted significant effects, the 4th treatment most significantly (DMR) at 6-months ($P < 0.05$) reduced BMI, mean arterial

pressure (MAP), FBS, total cholesterol, LDL-C, triglycerides, perceived stress scale (PSS) score, dizziness handicap inventory (DHI) score; and most significantly increased HDL-C, 10-item Connors-Davidson resilience score and visual acuity, with improvement in MMSE accompanied with decreased incidence of URTIs. With increased stress, ageing and central nervous pathologies, there may be decrease of vitamin D receptor responsiveness coupled with depreciation of the GABAergic/glutamatergic ratio. This imbalance of inhibitory- to -excitatory coupling is known to be a causative factor in vertigo/dizziness, and neurodevelopmental/neuropsychiatric/neurodegenerative diseases. Tea forms of phyto-

derived GABAergic enhancers or vitamin D3-mimetics which are safe and non-addictive with or without vitamin D supplementation upregulate the VDR-GABA-NO-cGMP-PKG pathway and may prove to be additive to present agents for treatment not only of vertigo but also for attenuation of endothelial-/neuronal dysfunction - mediated aetiologically-confounding systemic disorders crucial in vertigo causation. These mediators of the pro-survival VDR- GABA-eNOS-cGMP-PKG signalling pathway may be the ‘GABA therapy’ and ‘fountain of youth’/’dew of youth’ restorative for their unique role in whole body-homeostasis that is dependent on an efficient brain-organ interaction implicated in regulation of the neuro-endocrine-immune-metabolic network; and thus deserve compelling attention.

KEYWORDS: Vertigo, GABA, VDR, eNOS, cGMP, Phyto-derived vitamin D mimetics.

INTRODUCTION

Vertigo is a percepto-cognitive illusion of a motion-associated spinning or twirling sensation which is both subjective and objective because it is typically an ‘imposed’ phenomenon in which the self and the environment seem out of tune with reality. It may also be described as a subjective-cum-objective aberration, a false belief or hallucination of a process involving the self and the ambience. Peripheral cause of vertigo (peripheral vestibular disease) such as benign paroxysmal positional vertigo (BPPV) is the most common diagnosis in dizzy patients.^[1]

Dizziness may be an imprecise term for a range of sensations, from the minor to the significant. Dizziness, at the same time, may refer to a sense of disorientation in space, vertigo or even light-headedness, disequilibrium or giddiness. The causes of the symptom dizziness may be broken down into four main categories: vertigo, presyncope/syncope (which is usually due to temporary reduction in cerebral blood flow), disequilibrium or distorted sense of stability which is commonly due to frailty, and nonspecific symptoms such as dehydration or disturbance in the stress axis. While about 20-40% of people have dizziness, only about 7.5-10% have vertigo (<https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov>).^[2]

THE SIZE OF THE PROBLEM

In the UK, it is estimated that 5 out of every 1,000 people consult their GP each year because of vertigo. The prevalence rises with age accounting for one of the commonest causes of primary physician visit in patients over 74 years. In developed countries, over 25% of 50 - 64-year-olds may experience dizziness and everyday stress via Hypothalamic-Pituitary-

Adrenal axis (HPA) dysregulation has a role to play. By the age of 80, a significant percentage of people would experience vertigo with women being more affected. Vertigo may have an inherent problem of under-reporting because a lot of patients, except it is seriously interfering with their occupation, may see it as an unfortunate and incomprehensible personal problem or tragedy.

The problem of vertigo/dizziness is exacerbated by the pandemic of vitamin D deficiency or insufficiency which affects 35-53% of the world population. The problem may be worse in sub-Saharan Africa where malnutrition, drug misuse induced or heat stress linked orthostatic hypotension, hyper-viscosity syndrome induced deficient brain oxygen supply due to sickle cell disease, thalassaemia, malaria; iron deficiency induced hypercoagulable state, and hookworm-anaemia induced chronic blood loss are common.

The potpourri of lesser-known aetiological factors that may induce vertigo/dizziness include dehydration, gymnastic twisties or loss of spatial awareness and control, sports-associated concussions or mild traumatic brain injury (mTBI), non-diabetic related cyclical hypoglycaemia, the subclavian-steal syndrome, contusions-induced traumatic brain injury, barotrauma or the specific alternobaric vertigo and neck injuries. In the ascendancy is the increasing cancer incidence-associated erythrocytosis, leucostasis and paraproteinaemia-induced sludging in the circulation which may be associated with the pathobiology involved in causation of vertigo/dizziness.^[3,4,5,6,7]

PRESENT MEDICATIONS FOR VERTIGO

Present medications for vertigo include antihistamines (such as cyclizine, meclizine, promethazine, dimenhydrinate) which reduce the spinning sensation and associated nausea; drugs specifically for nausea (such as ondansetron, metoclopramide); benzodiazepines which enhance GABAergic signalling (such as lorazepam, clonazepam, diazepam) to suppress vestibular symptoms; prochlorperazine (anti-dopaminergic) for severe nausea; betahistine for Meniere's disease (eMedicine health).

This article highlights, for the first time, the beneficial effect of non-classical flumazenil insensitive GABAergic enhancers which are phyto-bioactive non-addictive agents in vertigo management. Also, the role of vitamin D3 supplementation in the aged is mentioned copiously as a veritable agent for vertigo management after interrogation on vitamin D status

as serum levels of total 25(OH)D greater than 30 ng/ml may be deemed sufficient (2024 Endo. Soc. Guidelines).

Adults over 70 years old may safely be on supplementary 1,000 IU of vitamin D3 daily though much higher doses have been used for treatment for various diseases such as psoriasis, asthma, rickets, osteomalacia, rheumatoid arthritis and tuberculosis (<https://www2.hse.ie>) without the risk of persistent hypercalcemia.^[8] Investigators have noted the need for the population to be vitamin D3 and magnesium replete for magnesium is vital for the synthesis, activation, transport and receptor function of vitamin D3.^[9,10] Normal adult values for serum magnesium are 1.46 – 2.68 mg/dl or 0.75 – 0.95 mmol/L. At baseline 25(OH)D level below 30 ng/ml, magnesium supplementation has enhancement value on vitamin D level but shows decremental effect at baseline 25(OH)D levels more than 30 to 50 ng/ml implying a bimodal relationship. From our observation, dietary factors that are linked to low magnesium levels such as ultra-processed foods, MSG, salt, excessive caffeine in the aged and cured meat are also linked to high glutamate levels, thereby potentiating NMDA type glutamate receptor Ca²⁺-induced excitotoxicity (normally prevented by magnesium) that may be linked to vertigo/dizziness and other neurological disorders as well as insulin resistance.^[11,12]

Of the phyto-derived bioactive compounds, curcumin, resveratrol, melatonin, quercetin, or EGCG may be termed vitamin D-mimetics or adjuncts respectively because of their actions/modulatory actions on the VDR and they also enhance GABAergic signalling. Curcumin, carnosic acid or resveratrol may display similar roles to vitamin D3 on VDR-RXR heterodimerization and similar effects with vitamin D3 on the PTH/ calcium or FGF23/phosphate axes necessary for body calcium and phosphorus homeostasis (Haussler et al, 2009; Stone et al, 2015); and curcumin has been reported to enhance vitamin D levels.^[13,15]

Patients are to note that the use of turmeric, resveratrol or carnosic acid with ‘blood thinners’ such as antiplatelets, anticoagulants or even NSAIDs such as ibuprofen deserve proper supervision. Curcumin, resveratrol or even carnosic acid may interfere with platelet function and increase bleeding time if patient is on anticoagulants such as warfarin (coumarin, jantoven), apixaban (Eliquis), and rivaroxaban (Xarelto) or antiplatelet medications such as clopidogrel (Plavix, ticagrelor (brilinta), and aspirin which are also ‘blood thinners’ (<https://www.goodrx.com>).

CASE REPORTS

Below are 4 case reports on how some vertigo complaints have been managed in Oseghale Oriaifo Medical Centre, Ekpoma between 2024 to 2025 with vitamin D3 and its mimetics/synergists.

1. A 50-year-old patient presented to us in 2023 with a 10-year history of gradually – worsening dizziness, imbalance and feelings of his environment rotating around him. Attacks started after a diagnosed mini stroke (transient ischaemic attack) with a background of poorly controlled essential hypertension. Patient drank more than 3 cups of black coffee daily and ate mostly fast food. Recently, he himself was becoming so consumed by the increasingly frequent episodes of violent gyrations that getting out of bed was becoming impossible. Attacks that started infrequently (once a month) were becoming commonplace and more severe, accompanied by autonomic -cum- central nervous symptoms of nausea and loss of interest.

He admitted that the diuretic furosemide and the antihistamine, promethazine, which were initially helpful had recently proved ineffective. He had avoided hypnotics such as diazepam because of their side-effects. MRI reports indicated hypertension-induced ischaemic degenerative changes in territory of anterior inferior cerebellar artery akin to cerebral small vessel disease since there is poor collateral circulation in this area of the posterior circulation.

On examination, he was healthy-looking and overtly not agitated nor disorientated. The HINTS examination showed abnormal head impulse test, multidirectional nystagmus not suppressed by central fixation and misalignment on test of skew indicating peripheral + central causes of the vertigo.^[16,17] His blood pressure was elevated (MAP 134.80 mmHg); and Fasting Blood Sugar FBS was 134.72 mg/Dl. Triglyceride level was 226.12 mg/Dl and BMI was 32.20 Kg/m². Patient was advised to stop food items such as coffee, caffeinated teas, alcohol, foods containing monosodium glutamate such as snacks and fast foods, processed or cured meat, salt and high carbohydrate diets which can contribute to a hyper-glutamatergic state in ageing. Instant coffee in the aged may predispose to dry age-related macular degeneration (AMD) in those who are genetically susceptible;^[18] for patient had close relations with AMD. Ageing favours hyper-glutamatergic excitotoxicity in the vestibulo-ocular reflex pathway which contributes to vertigo. Also, in TIAs or stroke, a hyper-glutamatergic state is favoured by the ischaemic events. Additionally, areas of the brain involved in the cerebral small vessel disease of TIA or of ageing, hypertension, obesity

and cerebral amyloid angiopathy-associated TIAs and the associated white matter hyperintensities may project to the vestibulo-ocular reflex path and worsen vertigo over time.

In light of the above, the patient was advised to be on turmeric, lemon-ginger and black pepper teas which through their active ingredients, all decrease neuronal glutamate release by inhibiting glutaminase. The treatment significantly at 6-months ($P < 0.05$) reduced BMI, mean arterial pressure (MAP), FBS, total cholesterol, LDL-C, triglycerides, perceived stress scale (PSS) score, dizziness handicap inventory (DHI) score; but significantly increased HDL-C, 10-item Connors-Davidson resilience score and visual acuity (Table I); with improvement in MMSE accompanied with decreased incidence of URTIs.

These teas also enhance GABAergic neurotransmission which could help attenuate progression of the damage and increased inflammation due to cerebral small vessel disease. This is with the caveat that turmeric overdose may not only be vasculo-toxic and hepatotoxic but can also act to dysregulate immunomodulation.^[19, 20] The WHO therapeutic dose of curcumin for a 70 Kg body weight adult is 210mg which is equivalent to 2 - 3 teaspoonfuls daily of turmeric (<https://www.vivolife.co.uk>).

With the above regimen, the patient started to feel free of dizziness and vertigo after 2 weeks and has remained so.

2. Is there association between vertigo and glaucoma and how are they connected to the principal neurodegenerative disease, Alzheimer' disease of which mild cognitive impairment is usually the first presentation?

A 61-year-old man presented in 2022 with vertigo, optical coherence tomography (OCT)-diagnosed glaucoma and mild cognitive impairment. He had a 20-year history of dizziness, same as for Case 1 but with more tendency to falls. He noticed contraction of his visual fields of 5-year duration and was gradually losing memory for recent events. There was also slowly progressive early peripheral or cortical cataract of one of the eyes but what had impelled him to come to us was due to a fall in the church during an address.

It was not the usual fall for he lost consciousness for about 30 minutes or more. According to him, this was the most serious attack he had ever had. Patient has been on treatment for high blood pressure for over 25 years and since he was not very compliant with or adherent to his medication instructions or plan of action, he had always associated the vertigo and unsteady

gait with 'high blood pressure'. BMI was 34.82 Kg/m²; MAP was 138.56 mm/Hg; FBS 138.18; Cholesterol 254.60; LDL 236.26; Triglycerides 228.84 mg/Dl at presentation. Retinopathy with hypertension-induced spasms of the anterior inferior cerebellar artery territory of the posterior circulation which was suspected clinically can give this presentation of central vertigo.^[16,21,22]

The patient was advised to take his blood pressure medications regularly, to avoid food items which may contain salt/sugar, caffeine, MSG and placed on regular consumption of strawberry, green and chamomile teas. Resveratrol and anthocyanins in strawberries, L-theanine in green tea, apigenin in chamomile positively modulate GABAergic signalling and downregulate glutamatergic overdrive in vertigo. Epigallocatechin gallate in green tea is recently indicated to attenuate glaucoma progression. It is resveratrol in strawberries that is being spotlighted for glaucoma treatment. Resveratrol prevents retinal ganglion cell apoptosis via upregulating SirtI and OpaI and decreasing ErbB2 {HER2} protein after ischaemic lesions. Resveratrol negatively impacts retinal ganglion cell apoptosis via upregulating PI3K/Akt pathway which increases cell survival and downregulates the HIF-I alpha/VEGF and p38/p53 pathways. Resveratrol also decreases oxidative stress markers in trabeculae meshwork of glaucoma patients to decrease IOP. Maybe, most importantly resveratrol like curcumin from turmeric may help with the reduction of β - amyloid toxicity, and degradation of hyperphosphorylated tau protein in the vitreous fluid of glaucoma patients. The effect on tau protein and β -amyloid makes resveratrol relevant for glaucoma and Alzheimer's disease. The treatment significantly at 6-months ($P < 0.05$) reduced BMI, mean arterial pressure (MAP), FBS, total cholesterol, LDL-C, triglycerides, perceived stress scale (PSS) score, dizziness handicap inventory (DHI) score; but significantly increased HDL-C, 10-item Connors-Davidson resilience score and visual acuity (Table I); with improvement in MMSE accompanied with decreased incidence of URTIs.

Patient started to notice improvement after 3 weeks of the regular medications and the herbal tea consumption. Vertigo disappeared, blurring of vision was attenuated and visual acuity improved from 20/120 to 20/80. According to patient, there was also some improvement in memory and focus.

3. A 68-year-old man was diagnosed with ataxia associated with vertigo and bladder outlet dyssynergia in 2021 and, according to him, no treatment has been satisfactory. With the vertigo, he has been having illusions of a distorted self and environment. Ataxic gait, though

mild, added to the misery which was compounded by the ultrasound/cystometry-diagnosed bladder outlet dyssynergia. A hypertensive recently diagnosed with early glaucoma; he had become non-adherent to his medications. The vertigo responded somewhat to lorazepam but it had made him sleepy and inattentive. Patient also complained about lack of a home since the wife left him in 2019 due to problems with erectile dysfunction attributed to blood pressure medications. On presentation, BMI was 34.54 Kg/m²; MAP 154.48 mm/Hg; FBS 138.18; Cholesterol 236.26; LDL 236.26; Triglycerides 228.84 mg/dL.

Our diagnosis was stress- and hypertension- induced central vertigo, bladder outlet dyssynergia due to dysregulation of pontine micturition centre, erectile dysfunction and reactive depression. In fact, patient admitted he has been on ineffective traditional drugs for erectile dysfunction. Peripheral vertigo was excluded with the Dix- Hallpike test which revealed no provoked nystagmus in the test. There was no history of Meniere's disease or vestibular migraine in which there would be aura and headache nor was there any tinnitus or hearing abnormalities. In any case, Meniere's disease is more common in females and tends to disappear around the age of 60 years. MRI Head had confirmed white matter hyperintensities due to improperly managed hypertension.

The addition of low dose of the phosphodiesterase 5 inhibitor tadalafil (5 mg of tadalafil every other day) to rosemary + chamomile teas in combination with his blood pressure and glaucoma medications gave patient a new lease of life. Patient's problems from the centrally induced vertigo, blood pressure fluctuations, erectile dysfunction and depression were severely mitigated. This treatment more significantly than group 2 results at 6-months ($P < 0.05$) reduced BMI, mean arterial pressure (MAP), FBS, total cholesterol, LDL-C, triglycerides, perceived stress scale (PSS) score, dizziness handicap inventory (DHI) score; but more significantly increased HDL-C, 10-item Connors-Davidson resilience score and visual acuity (Table I); with improvement in MMSE accompanied with decreased incidence of URTIs. In fact, there was no more vertigo, ataxia or drop attacks. Tadalafil and rosemary-derived vitamin D3-mimetic, carnosic acid may synergistically enhance the vitagene and global antioxidant Nrf2, attenuates lipid peroxidation, ADMA and NADPH oxidase 4 levels, increases angiogenesis in bone via upregulating the NO-cGMP-PKG pathway, enhances VDR in bone, and increases catalase and glutathione levels, effects that may be synergistic with that of vitamin D3 (<https://hmdb.ca>);^[23,24,25] actions which stand to mandate the repurposing of tadalafil for various disorders.

4. Patient presented as in first case. On presentation, BMI was 34.50 Kg/m²; MAP 158.28 mm/Hg; FBS 136.78; Cholesterol 238.36; LDL 232.76; triglycerides 251.60 mg/dL.

Patient responded well to the combination of vitamin D 3 (1000 IU daily) supplementation to the strawberry and turmeric teas. This treatment most significantly at 6-months ($P < 0.05$) reduced BMI, mean arterial pressure (MAP), FBS, total cholesterol, LDL-C, Triglycerides, perceived stress scale (PSS) score, dizziness handicap inventory (DHI) score; but most significantly increased HDL-C, 10-item Connors-Davidson resilience score and visual acuity (Table I); with improvement in MMSE accompanied with decreased incidence of URTIs.

There were some notable differences: visual acuity improved more; patient was more interested in daily activities and blood triglycerides decreased more. There was greater decrease in appetite and dosage requirement for anti-hypertensive drugs decreased. There was decrease in incidence of precordial pains of angina, decreased residual urine from bladder outlet dyssynergia and increased executive function as manifested by the enhanced alertness and effective integrated information processing and work speed. This is reflected in the greatly improved MMSE score and most significantly reduced DHI score at 6 months. Patient's middle finger stenosing tenosynovitis (trigger-finger) also resolved completely.

Dose of vitamin D3 is titrated to age and those above 70 years would generally benefit with a dose of 800-1,000 IU (25 µg) orally daily. (webMD: <https://www.webmd.com>, much lower than the amount of 10,000-25,000 IU per day made naturally from the action of sunshine on the precursor molecule 7-dehydrocholesterol {McCullough et al, 2019). This amount of vitamin D may be negatively impacted by melanin in dark-skin persons which causes less efficient conversion of 7-dehydrocholesterol to pre-vitamin D3.^[26]

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS

Statistical analysis was done with unpaired t-test and one-way ANOVA using SSPS version 17 for analysis. (Table I)

Table I: Effect Of Vitamin D, Vitamin D Mimetics/Synergists on visual acuity, infection rates; and neurological and cardiometabolic parameters.

Treatments (1-4)	Turmeric + lemon-ginger + black pepper			Green, strawberry, chamomile			Tadalafil + rosemary, chamomile			Vitamin D3 + turmeric + strawberry		
	0	3	6	0	3	6	0	3	6	0	3	6
BMI (Kg/m²)	32.20 ± 1.56	31.75 ± 1.88	29.20 ± 1.88	34.82±2.62	31.76±1.84	30.68±1.98	34.54±3.56	31.84±2.78	31.23±1.80	34.50±2.49	32.82±2.46	31.56±1.80*
MAP (mm/Hg)	134.80±1.84	100.88±0.90	95.78±1.68	138.56±1.76	98.62±1.38	96.24±2.68	154.48±1.86	106.58±1.24	94.34±1.66	158.28±1.36	106.56±2.62	92.68±1.44*

FBS (mg/dL)	134.72±1.56	105.34±1.38	98.84±1.82	138.18±1.68	106.54±1.92	86.38±0.36	136.78±1.76	104.98±2.42	86.46±1.56	145.58±1.46	101.86±1.80	84.56±1.82*
Cholesterol (mg/dL)	286.42±4.82	204.56±5.26	201.84±6.42	254.64±3.88	216.82±4.66	198.58±4.84	248.60±1.86	202.98±2.68	188.88±4.92	238.76±2.36	194.48±2.80	186.92±4.46*
HDL (mg/dL)	44.16±0.88	50.18±1.80	50.26±1.61	48.64±1.89	52.84±2.18	52.86±2.67	48.54±1.80	49.12±1.26	58.38±2.36	46.80±2.34	49.96±1.22	62.18±1.48*
LDL (mg/dL)	228.16±4.88	115.28±3.85	99.32±2.97	236.26±4.54	118.46±5.20	98.68±4.21	224.88±2.39	120.26±3.29	96.74±6.20	232.76±5.88	114.56±4.31	95.58±5.29*
Triglycerides (mg/dL)	226.12±6.82	142.28±5.21	112.60±4.44	228.84±2.94	122.48±3.66	110.68±5.25	238.56±7.34	128.54±6.88	98.62±5.33	251.60±4.76	100.36±6.18	98.61±5.93*
PSS score	35.71±0.56	24.56±1.80	13.48±2.61	35.32±1.83	24.62±5.62	13.80±4.18	35.32±4.26	26.48±5.39	14.84±4.12	36.80±5.22	26.42±5.43	12.36±5.96*
Resilience score	27.26±3.66	29.44±1.92	31.96±2.08	24.60±2.38	26.58±1.72	30.66±3.49	24.86±2.41	28.46±1.89	32.86±1.46	24.28±1.29	29.12±1.85	34.58±3.26*
Visual acuity	20/120	20/80	20/80	20/120	20/80	20/80	20/120	20/80	20/40	20/120	20/80	20/40*
Dizziness Handic. Invent. score	56.75±3.68	28.64±6.47	10.46±3.90	48.86±5.14	30.46±4.78	10.42±3.25	56.38±3.88	32.58±4.68	8.64±3.24	56.39±4.53	25.68±4.26	8.32±3.21*
MMSE	21	22	26	24	24	26	23	25	28	22	26	29
9-mo URTI Infection rate	3	0	0	3	0	0	3	0	0	4	0	0

Table I: Values are expressed as means ± SD. Differences in means was considered significant if $P < 0.05$. DMR post-hoc test was used to calculate the order of significance. Order of significance in reducing BMI, MAP, FBS, Total Cholesterol, LDL-C, Triglycerides, Perceived Stress Scale (PSS) score, Dizziness Handicap Inventory (DHI) score; and increasing HDL-C, Resilience (10-item CD test) score, and visual acuity was Group 4 (vitamin D + strawberry + turmeric teas) > 3 (tadalafil + rosemary + chamomile teas) > 2 (green, strawberry + turmeric teas) > 1 (turmeric +lemon-ginger + black pepper teas), showing the Group 4 as most significant(*).

RESULTS

All the treatment groups significantly at 6-months ($P < 0.05$) reduced BMI, MAP, FBS, total cholestertol, LDL-C, triglycerides, PSS score, DHI score; but significantly increased HDL-C, 10-item Connors-Davidson resilience score and visual acuity. Group 4 results were most significant. The treatment groups also lessened the incidence of upper respiratory tract infections and enhanced cognition as per the MMSE scores, but this sample size is not enough for statistical analysis of MMSE scores (see Table I). Not shown is the result of a preliminary test which indicated the treatment groups lowered CRP values at 3, 6 months.

Review Of The Aetiologically-Confounding Systemic Disorders In Vertigo/Dizziness Which Are Ameliorated By Vitamin D, Vitamin D-Mimetics/Synergists.

Vitamin D3- VDR-GABA-eNOS-cGMP-PKG signalling is vaso-protective and neuroprotective

Multiple lines of research indicate that enhancement of GABAergic signalling, which is negatively affected by ageing, is neuroprotective as well as endothelial-protective. GABA has been noted to be a silent regulator of whole-body homeostasis with broadly positive impact on neuro-cardio-immunometabolic functions.^[27] Neuronal GABA and endothelial-derived GABA are essential for angiogenesis, neuronal migration and proliferation, BBB integrity, and neuron-to-vascular communication at the neurovascular unit (neurovascular coupling) via nitric oxide release. GABAergic signalling enhancement may be obligatory for correction of some neurodevelopmental disorders and for recovery after a stroke or ministroke. Vitamin D enhances glutamate decarboxylase activity, glutamate neuronal uptake, inhibits glutaminase like turmeric-derived curcumin or chamomile-derived quercetin and increases GABA/glutamate ratio in brain areas associated with the vestibulo-ocular reflex. Vitamin D also functions to enhance the synthesis, release and receptor activity of GABA.^[28,35]

The yeoman's service of vitamin D3 in Nutri-epigenetics is fully underlined by the reciprocity of vitamin D signalling to the transcription factor nVDR and epigenetic mechanisms^[36] The ligand-dependent transcription factor VDR has the ligand, the vitamin D hormone ($1\alpha,25(\text{OH})_2\text{D}_3$) to activate its ability to regulate gene expression, acting with coactivators and corepressors.

Vascular smooth muscle cells (VSMCs) display plasticity (phenotypic switching) between a contractile quiescent state and a dedifferentiated synthetic state marked by increased proliferation and migration. VSMC irreversible dysregulated phenotypic switching is a fundamental process in the pathology of atherosclerosis, chronic hypertension, stroke, vascular aortic aneurysms, restenosis, graft failure and, indirectly, cardiomyopathy and heart failure. Factors of the vitamin D3/mimetics-VDR-GABA-eNOS-cGMP-PKG signalling pathway such as vitamin D3, GABA, quercetin /resveratrol/turmeric/EGCG, endothelial nitric oxide, cGMP, PKG maintain VSMC plasticity via inhibition of macrophages differentiating into foam cells with cholesterol efflux failure, inhibition of endothelial to mesenchymal transition, anti-inflammatory effects, regulation of growth and proliferation, modulation of extracellular matrix (ECM), renin-angiotensin-aldosterone (RAAS) system

regulation and AMPK activation. They repress dedifferentiation and trans differentiation of vascular smooth muscle cells (VSMCs) into a phenotypic non-contractile or synthetic state marked by increased proliferation, migration, altered gene expression, extracellular matrix secretion, apoptosis, senescence, and osteogenic/chondrocytic transdifferentiation. This synthetic state which favours cardiovascular diseases and indirectly vertigo is enhanced by epigenetic factors, altered mechanotransduction, insulin resistance, high glucose, cholesterol, oxidized-LDL, RAAS, endothelin-I, inflammatory cytokines and growth factors such as TNF-alpha, HMGBI and PDGF-BB, inflammasome activation, proprotein convertase subtilisin/kexin type 9 (PCSK9), dysregulation of Notch I and aberrant β -catenin signalling. For example, vitamin D3, quercetin, resveratrol or curcumin may inhibit Notch I and decrease cholesterol and PCSK9 to enhance plaque stabilization and also prevent VSMC transdifferentiation and dedifferentiation.^[37,40] These actions may be synergistic with the anti-inflammatory effects of rosuvastatin which may be paramount in plaque stabilisation and regression; and with those of vitamin K2 which via one of the vitamin K2-dependent protein, matrix Gla proteins, (MGP), enhance calcium mobilization from vascular plaques and other extra-osseous sites to bone.

Now, the main excitatory motor neurons in the CNS found in the cerebral cortex, hippocampus and amygdala essential for vision-motor control, learning and memory utilize glutamate as transmitter. The excitatory actions of glutamate, which is also employed by photoreceptor rods and cones, is ably and efficiently modulated by GABA(ergic) signalling. By modulating excitability and synaptic transmission in pyramidal cells, GABAergic activities control firing patterns, spike – timing, spike-timing-dependent-plasticity (necessary for memory encoding), and information-processing capabilities of pyramidal cells. Increased GABA level is noted to be associated with higher visual discrimination, lower susceptibility to distractions and stronger surround suppression. So, it is not surprising that because of the criticality of GABA or GABAergic signalling to the workings of the CNS that 60-75% of all synapses in the CNS are GABAergic.^[41,44]

Rampant hypertension and risk of vertigo

The metabolic syndrome, which is a cluster of metabolic risk factors of abdominal obesity, atherogenic dyslipidaemia (high triglycerides and low-density lipoproteins, low high-density lipoproteins), hypertension, type 2 diabetes and a prothrombotic state) is rampant in developing economies. The situation is fuelled by poverty and ignorance; consequently

diagnosis, management and follow-up of high blood pressure cases becomes an uphill task. In the cases presented above, hypertension was associated. Workers have estimated that in sub-Saharan Africa, hypertension has a crude prevalence in adults of 21.1%. and that vertigo may be present in about 35% of hypertensive cases. In developed countries, vertigo may be more often a geriatric syndrome,^[45] co-existing with other co-morbidities. Metabolic syndrome risk factors, osteoporosis, decreased vitamin D, atherosclerosis, metabo-cerebrovascular diseases such as metabolic dysfunction- associated steatotic liver disease (MASLD), ear surgery, use of ototoxic drugs and Meniere's disease are some of the secondary causes of BPPV.^[37]

Caffeine, salt and hypertension-induced risk factors

A range of vascular issues may ensue after consumption of coffee/caffeine or even monosodium glutamate-laced diet. Acute intoxication with caffeinated drinks may cause hypertension-induced arterial spasms, arterial stiffness, arterial dissection, decreased arterial velocities and retinopathy.

Increased Na⁺ and water in the body via epithelial sodium channels (ENaC) in aldosterone sensitive distal nephron (ASDN) and rostral ventromedial medulla (RVM)/choroid plexus; in concert with ENaCs in antigen-presenting cells (APCs) may induce reactive oxygen species (ROS) or lipid peroxidation species. These may signal to NLRP3 inflammasome and PKC and cause NADPH oxidase activation to induce oxidative stress, renal inflammation and hypertension.^[46,49]

Hypertensive stimuli including angiotensin II, sympathetic outflow and dietary salt and caffeine excess lead to increased NADPH oxidase- dependent ROS formation by APCs. ROS induce the formation not only of advanced glycation end-products (AGEs) formation but also induce the formation of isolevuglandins which are immunogenic and activate APCs to produce inflammatory cytokines. Isolevuglandins are markers of oxidative stress and potently form protein covalent adducts (lipid peroxidation end-products) which are implicated in glaucoma, cardiovascular diseases, hypertension, atrial fibrillation, and autoimmunity. The posterior circulation is favoured site for arteriosclerosis.^[50,53]

Drug addiction, hypertension and protective effect of vitamin D3 and its mimetics

Drugs of addiction can precipitate sodium and water retention to cause or aggravate hypertension and resistance to anti-hypertensive drugs.^[54] Amphetamines, cocaine, alcohol may induce vitamin D deficiency, dysregulate mitochondrial electron transport (ET) chain-

ROS-oxidative stress pathway to exacerbate angiotensin II overactivity and its deleterious consequences on myocardial remodelling. Excessive alcohol causes RAAS imbalance which further worsens alcohol addiction by increasing oxidative stress and increased dopaminergic activity in ventral tegmental area of the brain.^[55,56] GABA or non-classical GABA enhancers (such as resveratrol or curcumin) administration may benefit alcohol addicts, and indirectly opioid addicts since alcohol induces opioid release in VTA, partly by the GABA enhancers decreasing inflammatory cytokines and also by attenuating hepatotoxic effect of alcohol metabolites.^[57,58]

Vitamin D or its mimetics which signal to GABA such as curcumin and quercetin stand to benefit patients with drug addiction by preventing relapse and drug reinstatement. Vitamin D facilitates M2 polarisation, enhance decrease of inflammatory cytokines, increase BDNF, and triggering receptor expressed on myeloid cells 2 (TREM2) in helping to clear amyloid peptides via phagocytosis. Vitamin D reduces tau phosphorylation and A β peptides and could also attenuate the effect of cocaine-induced brain inflammation by increasing soluble triggering receptor expressed on myeloid cells 2 (sTREM2) in early Alzheimer's disease-induced mild cognitive impairment. Thus, there is a potential and significant role for vitamin D or its mimetics in preventing and treating impulse control disorders, behavioural addictions and substance use disorders; and the ominous effects vis-à-vis hypertension and metabolic syndrome.^[59,62]

Additionally, activation of cGMP by C-natriuretic peptide attenuates drug addiction due to cocaine by reducing the immediate early gene EGR-I in dopaminergic structures linked to reward, pleasure and addiction.^[63] cGMP can produce an inhibitory effect on dopamine release in brain structures involved in addiction but tadalafil in alcohol addicts may precipitate low blood pressure and increase stroke risk; moreover PDE-5 is not well distributed in brain reward areas.^[64]

Decreased incidence of hypertension and related illnesses with augmentation of the vitamin D /cGMP-eNOS-cGMP axis

The vitamin D /cGMP axis decrease appetite by upregulating leptin sensitivity and enhancing Protein YY and proopiomelanocortins,^[65,69] while enhancing the anti-arrhythmogenic and β -adrenoceptor effect of the ANS on the heart.^[70] Vitamin D upregulates the anti-hypertensive (vasodilator), antifibrotic, antithrombotic, antihypertrophic, anti-inflammatory and immune-regulating ACE2-Ang (1-7) MasR pathway to counter the negative effects of ACE/Ang

II/ATIR axis in hypertension, NAFLD/MAFLD, cognition, infections, cancer and cardiac remodelling.^[71,72] Vitamin D also attenuates the negative sequelae of obesity induced decreases in 25-hydroxylase generation of 25-hydroxyvitamin D and obesity-induced increases in uric acid levels [Personal Communication, 201].^[73,74]

In parallel, the GABA-eNOS pathway inhibits central actions of angiotensin and angiotensin-induced cardiac hypertrophy.^[75,76] Turmeric derived curcumin, strawberry-derived resveratrol, melatonin, lignans and quercetin, chamomile-derived quercetin, green tea-derived EGCG enhance VDR activity either as mimetics or synergists. Curcumin, melatonin, quercetin, patuletin, anthocyanins and resveratrol may be termed flumazenil-insensitive non-classical GABAergic enhancers that may not have misuse or abuse potential because they do not act on the αI -site of the GABA_A-receptors.^[77]

The axis decreases renin release and blunts the effect of RAAS and of the L-type ryanodine sensitive calcium channels. It inhibits the arrhythmogenic effects of β -adrenoceptor stimulation. Especially cGMP and its potentiator tadalafil increases natriuresis by i) inhibiting type 3 Na/H* exchanger, 2) inhibiting the NK2CL cotransporter in thick ascending limb of Henle, 3) blunting the ENaC in distal urinary ducts.^[78]

The vitamin D and its mimetics upregulate the GABA- eNOS- cGMP-PKG axis which is renoprotective via anti-fibrotic, anti-thrombotic and anti-cancer effects, and fine-tunes insulin release, while also inhibiting L-type ryanodine calcium channels.^[79,82] Vitamin D receptor agonists are protective in chronic kidney disease for they increase klotho levels; an effect which indirectly lead to decreases in blood pressure.^[83] Like the vitamin D analogues alfacalcidol and paricalcitol, phyto-derived vitamin D3 mimetics may induce less hypercalcemia than calcitriol when administered for chronic kidney disease treatment.^[84] Apart from its blood pressure-lowering effect, the cGMP potentiator, tadalafil attenuates high-salt induced upregulation of plasminogen activator inhibitor-I (PAI-I) which causes increased alpha-smooth muscle actin (α -SMA) and myofibroblast differentiation-induced glomerulosclerosis (renal fibrosis),^[85] a renoprotective effect which may be synergistic with that of vitamin D3 in preventing fibrocontractive diseases such as ESKD; a process not preventable by present anti-hypertensive drugs. The net effect of vitamin D and its mimetics as well as cGMP potentiation by tadalafil may be increased nephroprotection and decreased need for antihypertensive drugs as we have seen in our case reports.

Also, the relatively low but significant potassium in chamomile may be additive with potassium-rich foods such as avocados, spinach and bananas to counter high salt-induced hypertension; and this may decrease hypertension risk by 25%.^[86]

VDR-GABA-eNOS-cGMP pathway decrease insulin resistance and mitochondrial dysfunction

In fact, workers have demonstrated that vitamin D and peroxisome proliferator activated receptor -alpha (PPAR-alpha) display overlapping pattern of expression to enhance osteocalcin-induced insulin release, increase insulin sensitivity, decrease central brain insulin resistance, mitochondrial biogenesis, fatty acid oxidation, and muscle glucose uptake via GLUT4 transporter.^[87,88]

These actions are also displayed by the vitamin D mimetics or synergists curcumin, quercetin, lignans, carnosic acid, resveratrol, and EGCG found in turmeric, strawberries, chamomile and green tea respectively. Apigenin, a flavonone from chamomile, at low doses has a second-order or metamodulatory role on GABA receptors to indirectly enhance the actions of vitamin D, for example by downregulating glutamatergic neurotransmission and enhancing insulin signalling pathway via AMPK activation.^[89,94]

Anthocyanins have been noted by workers to enhance GLP-I release from intestinal enteroendocrine L-cells. This helps to alleviate insulin resistance and induce beiging of white adipocytes.^[95] From very recent publication that pancreatic alpha-cells could also release GLP-I in the event of absence of normal production of glucagon or in aging/metabolic stress by the administration of sitagliptin/dapagliflozin, is it not conceivable that anthocyanins may also induce GLP-I release from alpha-cells under similar circumstances?^[96,97]

GABA-eNOS pathway increases insulin release, decreases insulinitis and proinflammatory cytokines. GABA increases regenerative ability of islet cells to also show benefit in type I diabetes in mouse and clinical models by enhancing α -cell to β -cell transdifferentiation and decreasing autoimmune processes; while attenuating neuropathy, retinopathy and nephropathy.^[98]

The cGMP potentiator tadalafil has shown benefit in hepatic steatosis by enhancing PPAR-alpha.^[99,100,101]

Vitamin D and cGMP potentiators are beneficial in lipotoxicity which is linked to hypertension

Lipotoxicity is a part of the metabolic syndrome cluster of risk factors. It results from the accumulation of lipid intermediates in non-adipose tissue leading to cellular dysfunction and apoptosis. The tissues mostly affected are the kidneys, liver, heart and skeletal muscle. Thus lipotoxicity, which worsens with age, is a key factor in the development of insulin resistance, atherosclerosis, cardiomyopathy and CKD.

Vitamin D lowers triglycerides which is a surrogate for atherosclerotic cardiovascular disease that is favoured by obesity and insulin resistance. The NO-cGMP-PKG axis plays pivotal role in regulation of glucose and fat metabolism to downregulate free fatty acids and hyperglycaemia which are toxic for pancreatic B-cells.^[102,103]

The vitamin D-GABA axis decreases triglyceride and cholesterol build-up in liver thereby impacting lipotoxicity and this is partly mediated via the inhibition of PCSK9 which further enables the LDL-C receptor-mediated LDL-C uptake.^[104,105,106] They thus may help with decreasing triglyceride-rich lipoprotein remnants (TRL).

Hypertriglyceridemia favours more atherogenic lipoproteins such as TRL. TRL and their remnants from VLDL and chylomicrons have a pernicious nature in being able to penetrate to the subendothelial layer of blood vessels to create a sustained inflammatory cascade leading to myocardial infarction and valvular stenosis.

If cGMP potentiates fatty acid oxidation and decrease triglyceride synthesis, they stand to enhance decrease in TRL and their complications.^[107] Tadalafil activates AMPK via the NO-H2S pathway and has been found to decrease Apo B/Apo-AI ratio in mouse models and human volunteers.^[108,109,110] It is not counter-intuitive to add tadalafil (which enhances GABA release via nitric oxide) subchronically or chronically at low doses to present regimens such as gemfibrozil and monoclonal antibodies (evolocumab,alirocumab)/antisense oligonucleotides, PCSK9 inhibitors for management of TRL remnant- or the genetically determined apolipoprotein (a)-induced complications.^[111,112,113] In low-income settings saddled with poor availability of the more effective monoclonal antibodies to manage hypertriglyceridemias, judicious non-sexual tadalafil + vitamin D3 use may be worthwhile.^[114]

Vitamin D3 is critical determinant of the direct and indirect effects of lipids on microglia function in Alzheimer's disease, metabolic syndrome and aging

Vitamin D3 has been shown by workers to be a critical determinant in enhancing the microglia response for damage control in lipotoxicity and chronic inflammation. Vitamin D3 via nVDR and mVDR facilitates the M2 polarisation and β -amyloid uptake by human microglia and enhances hippocampal and cerebellar microglia anti-inflammatory state. It carries this out in a TREM2-/ApoE2-/lipoprotein lipase- (lpl-) and Sirt6-dependent manner as opposed to its effect on ApoE4. Vitamin D3 and tadalafil activate AMPK to enhance microglial lipophagy thus preventing microglial lipid droplet accumulation which contributes to the buildup of TREM1 involved in diabetes-associated cognitive impairment (DACI), Alzheimer's disease and aging. Other diseases associated with lipid droplet accumulating microglia or lipid-laden microglia include obesity, tauopathies, demyelinating diseases such as multiple sclerosis, CNS injury, spinal cord injury, traumatic brain injury and glioblastoma. Via the AMPK pathway activation, vitamin D3 and tadalafil contribute indirectly to attenuating microglia lipid droplet (tracylglycerol) accumulation mediated by diacylglycerol-O-acyltransferase 2 (DGAT2), acyl-CoA synthetase long-chain (ACSL), fat storage inducing transmembrane protein 2 (FIT2) and angiopoietin-like 4 (ANGPTL4) as well as SREBP1 crucial in fomenting A β toxicity-induced cognitive decline and vertigo/dizziness.^[115-121] Decreasing lipid droplets formation may increase microglia amyloid- β uptake and phagocytosis of amyloid plaques thereby contributing to attenuation of pro-inflammatory cytokines and ROS.

Active compounds from some herbs that detoxify reactive oxygen species (ROS) and reactive carbonyl species (RCS) via modulating GABA and VDR

Herbal teas used in the present study include black pepper which has the active ingredients phenols, flavonoids, terpenes, terpene-alkaloids (terpenoids) including the pungent alkaloid piperine, amides, steroids, β -caryophyllene and lignans. Lemon has the active ingredient naringenin (a flavonoid), the flavonoid and vitamin D synergist rutin and hesperidin, a bioflavonoid and vitamin D synergist. Turmeric has phenolic compounds curcumin (non-classical GABAergic enhancer and vitamin D mimetic) and curcuminoids, terpenes, terpenoids, flavonoids, saponins, tannins and lignans. Rosemary tea provides the vitamin D mimetic diterpene, carnosic acid, principally.

Strawberries exhibit the phytochemicals resveratrol, (polyphenol, nonclassical GABAergic enhancer and vitamin D mimetic), anthocyanins responsible for the red coloration, terpenes, terpenoids, carotenoids lutein and zeaxanthin, flavonoid luteolin, quercetin, rutin, and the indoleamine melatonin. Vitamin D mimetics in strawberries include the flavonoid luteolin, the flavonoid quercetin, the indoleamine melatonin, the flavanol kaempferol, the anti-osteoporotic flavonoid fisetin. Carnosic acid which is converted to carnosol is the vitamin D mimetic in rosemary tea.^[122]

Green tea possesses the vitamin D synergist epigallocatechin gallate (also a non-classical GABAergic enhancer) as main polyphenol, melatonin, quercetin and fisetin as the other vitamin D mimetics; plus, other flavonoids, terpenes, alkaloids such as caffeine and volatile oils.

Chamomile displays the GABA-ergic enhancer apigenin, the vitamin D mimetics quercetin, melatonin, luteolin, patuletin, kaempferol, and fisetin. Other bioactive compounds include the sesquiterpene lactone parthenolide, flavonoids such as rutin, terpene-alkaloids, chlorogenic acid, α -bisabolol and chamazulene.

Green vegetables have the terpene alpha-limonene, the terpene opioid-and GABA-enhancing analgesic alpha-pinene, carotenoids (lutein and zeaxanthin), saponins, flavonoids and glucosinolates. Naringenin from lemon tea, as well as trivalent chromium.^[123,132]

Phyto-derived bioactive compounds attenuate reactive oxygen species- (ROS)- and reactive carbonyl species- (RCS)-induced complications

Turmeric-derived curcumin, strawberry-derived resveratrol, rosemary-derived carnosic acid and β -caryophyllene, green tea-derived EGCG, parthenolides and quercetin from chamomile and strawberry directly or indirectly enhance the vitamin D receptor signaling- induced antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, anti-angiogenic, immune-activating and endothelio-protective actions.^[133,136]

Curcumin, phenolates, terpenes, terpenoids. flavonoids, the phyto-stilbene resveratrol may chelate reactive carbonyl species thereby decreasing reactive carbonyl species-derived lipid peroxidation endproducts which may form protein adducts with proteins of the trabecular meshwork of the eye and optic nerve. By and large, the phytochemicals mentioned above and vitamin D3 decrease ROS and indirectly RCS which is downstream of ROS signalling. They

downregulate the inflammatory repertoire such as IL-1 β which may be significant in Meniere's disease and recurrent vertigo. IL-1 β blockers or glutaminase inhibitors such as vitamin D₃, curcumin, piperine, strawberries, chamomile and ginger decrease the accompanying hyperglutamatergic excitotoxicity associated with white matter hyperintensities in small vessel disease of the AICA territory and other brain areas involved with the vestibulo-ocular reflex path.^[137,138,139]

As a corollary, dizziness as a geriatric syndrome may be more related to white matter tracts relevant to balance or vestibular microangiopathy. The dizziness could also be from altered higher thalamocortical to vestibular processing and impaired structural white matter integrity. These phyto-derived bioactives also decrease glutamate toxicity in patients with endolymphatic hydrops. They enhance the actions of the vitagenes heme-oxygenase-I (HO-1) or HSP 32, HSP 72, sirtuins, glutathione, SOD2, thioredoxin and BCL-2 to preserve cellular homeostasis during stressful conditions.^[140,141]

Decreased muscle strength-induced falls in old age which complicates or compounds vertigo management may be due to age-induced lower vitamin D receptor signalling and may be remedied by vitamin D supplementation or with the use of its phyto-derived mimetics such as strawberry extract.^[142,149]

Protein misfolding is linked to glaucoma

Protein misfolding may link glaucoma, macular degeneration, Alzheimer's disease and vertigo in elderly people. Increasing amyloid- β and tau protein downregulate GABA_A receptors associated with decrease in neural specificity in glaucoma/macular degeneration patients and vertigo. GABAergic signalling enhances greater moment to moment signal variability in older adults to the level of young adults. There is significant role for vitamin D₃ and phytochemicals which enhance endogenous antioxidant defense; and they are in good stead in the downregulation of oxidative stress linked to protein misfolding.^[150]

Genetic and acquired causes of hyperhomocysteinemia may induce protein misfolding and also aggravate cardiovascular disease, neurodegenerative diseases and macular degeneration. Vitamin D and GABAergic signalling enhancers such as the vitamin D mimetics curcumin, carnosic acid and resveratrol attenuate plasma homocysteine levels. Raised plasma homocysteine causes eNOS uncoupling and downregulate cGMP signalling.^[151,152]

GABAergic signaling is enhanced directly or indirectly by these phytochemicals and vitamin D which boost insulin signaling, antioxidant defense and decrease microglial activation, hyperglutamatergic excitotoxicity in the vestibular-ocular pathway. Resveratrol for instance which also enhances vitamin D receptor signaling decreases glutamate uptake by neurons, decreases glutamate via ERK-Akt signaling, increases glutamine synthetase in astrocytes, increases the vitagene heme oxygenase (HO-I), helps mop up extrasynaptic glutamate and increase cAMP- PkA signaling to enhance GABAergic effects. Additionally, resveratrol decreases retinal ganglion cell loss and may even help in regeneration of retinal ganglion cells via increasing OpaI (a derivative of vitamin C), induces dephosphorylation of tau and decreasing ErbB2 -induced retinopathy in cases of hypoxia via decreasing HIF-1 α /VEGF and p38/p53 pathway and increasing PI3K/Akt pathway to prevent angiogenesis. Resveratrol and vitamin D3 – based nutraceuticals may attenuate age-related macular degeneration by preventing the degeneration of photoreceptors and retinal pigment epithelium when AREDS I and II drugs or when anti-VEGF injections of aflibercept have not worked. It is reported that this combination has prevented legal blindness.^[153]

GABA and vitamin D3 prevent retinal ganglion cell loss in diabetic retinopathy, attenuating vertigo and lessening the probability of vascular dementia/ age- associated otoconial dislodgement as in recurrent BPPV following a ministroke in the AICA territory.

Recently, it is recognized that the GABA to nitric oxide to cGMP to PKG to K_{ATP} signaling decrease oxidative stress and that phosphodiesterase 5 inhibitors decrease oxidative stress via cGMP which prevents retinal ganglion cell degeneration and is reported to be protective in glaucoma. In the same breath, nitric oxide enhances GABAergic neurotransmission.

The overlapping and at times synergistic effects of turmeric's curcumin, strawberry-derived resveratrol, lemon-derived naringenin, vitamin D and tadalafil in vertigo, and age-related diseases is due to GABA enhancement, antioxidative and anti-inflammatory effects of these agents.^[154,155]

The retinal protectants and antioxidants curcumin, carnosic acid, resveratrol, EGCG, β -caryophyllene, vitamin D3 and low-dose tadalafil suppress vertigo, attenuate age-related glaucoma and ED

The main active ingredient in turmeric is curcumin and its bioavailability is enhanced with the addition of black pepper which has the active ingredients piperine, β -caryophyllene and

lignans. Piperine increases the absorption and bioavailability of curcumin and vitamin D3. Gingerol from ginger's anti-inflammatory and anti-oxidant effects may be synergistic with vitamin D3. Naringenin modulated the vitamin D receptor's actions. Epigallo-catechin gallate from green tea induced patterns may induce changes in methylation patterns of DNA which can influence binding of VDR-RXR coupled to vitamin D response elements (VDREs) in promoter regions of target genes for genomic effects. The non-genomic fast actions of vitamin D3 are via membrane-bound VDR, membrane receptor protein disulphide isomerase A3, G-protein coupled receptors (GPCRs), MAPK, PKC and membrane-gated calcium channels, and phospholipase A2, for example, to effect osteoblast activity.^[156] Vitamin D3 non-genomic effect on neurons may involve inhibiting inward currents mediated by NMDA and kainite receptors.^[157]

Resveratrol as well as carnolic acid promote the heterodimerization of vitamin D with RXR via SIRT1 activation. Curcumin has significant action for it activates the VDREs like vitamin D itself.^[158,159] Curcumin and the volatile oil curcumol from turmeric enhance GABAergic signaling; while β -caryophyllene enhances GABAergic signaling indirectly. Curcumin alone or in combination with vitamin D3 increases GABA production from glutamate by the enzyme glutamic acid decarboxylase and decreasing catabolism of GABA by GABA transaminase and succinic semialdehyde dehydrogenase.^[160,161] Curcumin also has not insignificant effect in inhibiting phosphodiesterase-5 which indirectly increases GABAergic signaling via endothelial nitric oxide.^[162,163] The PD-5 inhibition by the synthetic tadalafil increases endothelial nitric oxide (eNOS) partly by preventing its uncoupling by oxidants including NOX4 and also enhances cyclic guanosine monophosphate (cGMP) necessary for retinal protection and vertigo suppression as shown in these reports.^[164] In men over 65 years, glaucoma, chronic ocular and vascular hypertension and erectile dysfunction are linked by increased oxidative stress and endothelial dysfunction.^[165] eNOS production in the inner retina and the nucleus of the tractus solitarius enhances GABA release via NO-cGMP-cyclic adenosine diphosphate ribose {cADPR) – Ca^{2++} pathway. Via these separate mechanisms, turmeric and tadalafil may display overlapping and synergistic effects in attenuating glaucoma and chronic ocular hypertension and vertigo since they would increase the GABA/glutamate ratio in the vestibulo-ocular axis and other brain areas.^[166,171]

Additional mechanism of action of phosphodiesterase 5 inhibitors in erectile dysfunction may be via decreasing oxidative stress. For in about 35% of erectile dysfunction cases, there may

be resistance to phosphodiesterase 5 inhibitors {PDE-5 Is) but they respond to antioxidants. PDE-5 inhibitors may decrease oxidative stress and endoplasmic reticulum stress via the cGMP-cAMP response element binding protein (CREB) and the Rho/ROCK signalings. Tadalafil decreases markers of apoptosis C/EBP homologous protein (CHOP); and the marker of decreased autophagy and cellular stress, the glucose regulated protein 78 or binding immunoglobulin protein (BIP) important in the unfolded protein response. Antioxidants may thus increase testicular testosterone by their antioxidant effects and enhance smooth muscle relaxation and endothelial function.^[172,179]

Resveratrol may not inhibit phosphodiesterase-5 but its anti-oxidant and anti-inflammatory effects may indirectly lead to PDE-5 inhibitory effects, ie via enhancing nitric oxide production and reducing superoxide production to indirectly enhance testicular testosterone. Studies also show that resveratrol also inhibits phosphodiesterase-5 via the NO-cGMP pathway.

Optimal vitamins D/A ratio is important for the actions of vitamins A and D. Vitamin A is synergistic with vitamin D at low concentrations. At high concentration's of vitamin A, it is antagonistic to vitamin D. Optimal vitamin D concentration enhances the efficacy of phosphodiesterase-5 inhibitors. Similar to vitamin D, the anti-oxidant role of vitamin A may enhance efficacy of phosphodiesterase inhibitors in pulmonary arterial hypertension and erectile dysfunction.^[180,181]

Vitamin D receptor signalling attenuate glaucoma and age-related macular degeneration

The mechanisms of vitamin D in age-related macular degeneration is multifaceted and involves modulatory activity in acute and chronic inflammation, decreasing adaptive immune and proliferative responses, enhancing antioxidant mechanisms, decreasing NF-kappaB - MMPs-I/2/7/9/13/14 – and VEGF-induced ECM degradation which enables the neovascularization of wet AMD. It may also inhibit amyloid-beta and influence programmed cell death and age-related increased CD^{NULL} T cells which enhance pro-inflammatory activities.^[182,183]

The anti-inflammatory effects of vitamin D involves decreasing IL-2 and T-bet induced upregulation of interferon-gamma. Adaptive immune responses are down-regulated by vitamin D by decreasing lymphocyte proliferation; and promoting differentiation of

monocytes to macrophages which enhance debris clearance from retinal pigment epithelium-bruch's membrane-choriocapillaris complex.^[184]

The anti-oxidant functions of vitamin D may also be influenced positively by its phototransduction derived products of pre-vitamin D₃, tachysterol and lumisterol. These include attenuating ROS and RCS by activating the vitagene Nrf2, which has global anti-oxidant role. The effects extend to decreasing MMP-9 involved in the neovascularization in wet – AMD and the exhibition of anti-viral effects against SARS-COV2 virus.^[185] Vitamin D attenuates amyloid-beta and innate lymphoid cells (ILCs such as natural killer cells) – induced programmed cell death and apoptosis regulation; also decreases microglial activation involved in increased glutamatergic signalling in vertigo.

Thus, acting alone or in combination with vitamin D, curcumin, resveratrol, EGCG, naringenin or even the synthetic tadalafil may attenuate AMD and even glaucoma thereby contributing immensely to lessen vertigo, whether centrally or peripherally mediated.

Additionally, vitamin D may also regulate the stress axis (hypothalamo-pituitary-adrenal axis) during acute and chronic stress which may induce vertigo. Vitamin D decreases cortisol, decreases epinephrine release via enhancing GABAergic signalling and may modulate serotonin levels.^[186,187]

Also, decreasing oxidative stress, attenuating chronic inflammation and angiogenesis and preventing endogenous nitric oxide uncoupling may be some of the ways vitamin D protects against glaucoma and glaucoma-induced degeneration of retinal ganglion cells. Formation of protein adducts by RCS-induced lipid peroxidation end products may hinder the workings of the trabecular meshwork leading to increased intraocular pressure.

Vitamin D protects against dry eye disease

Diseases of the ocular surface include dry eye disease (DED), which if left unchecked may lead to vertigo due to blurring of vision or even blindness. Conditions which may cause dry DED include age-related decrease in vitamins A and D. Severe forms of vitamin A deficiency is the cause of xerophthalmia. Diseases such as diabetes and autoimmune diseases may also cause DED. Examples of autoimmune diseases which are implicated are Reiter's syndrome (reactive arthritis, autoimmune-like disease), rheumatoid arthritis, multiple sclerosis and Sjogren's syndrome. The basic mechanism is loss of tolerogenic function of T_{REGS}.

(Teffector/ T_{reg} dyshomeostasis) commonly caused by cytokines which induce the T_{REGS} to lose their suppressor functions and assume proinflammatory phenotype. Other causes of DED include medications such as antihypertensives, hormonal changes, and inflammation or radiation. Increased tear evaporation may be caused by Meibomian gland dysfunction, smoking/ environmental pollutants, alcohol and allergy. Vitamin A supplementation or vitamin D (mast cell stabilizer) supplementation is helpful; especially vitamin A whose main function is to protect mucosal surfaces. These may be used alone or combined with other treatment like artificial tears.^[188]

Upside and preventable downside of tadalafil in retinal protection

Upregulation of NO – cGMP pathway increases blood supply to optic nerve head and protects retinal ganglion cell from degeneration. This pathway also helps protect against chronic ocular hypertension and glaucoma, maladies which affect over 80 million people worldwide.^[189] This is with the caveat that high doses of tadalafil may acutely decrease blood pressure in optic nerve head to precipitate non-arteritic ischaemic optic neuropathy (NAION), a condition worsened by diseases such as diabetes which increase oxidant stress. This high-dose tadalafil-induced hypotension may also contribute ischaemia of the deep capillary plexus (DCP), superficial capillary plexus (SCP), and radial peripapillary capillary plexus (RPC) which are the blood supply of the inner retina. Low doses of tadalafil may not be associated with this problem.

Low- dose tadalafil increases long-term nitric oxide secretion to also not only attenuate glaucoma but also to increase choroidal thickness and perfusion. Tadalafil-induced increase in choroidal and indirectly retinal blood flow may precipitate central serous chorioretinitis or central serous retinopathy (CSCR) and retinal exudates or even retinal pigment epithelium detachment. The concurrent usage of the intraocular pressure lowering drug latanoprost may offset these possible downsides of tadalafil which includes decreased capillary vessel density in the choriocapillaris supplying the choroid, retinal pigment epithelium and photoreceptor cells. Latanoprost increases autoregulation of choroidal blood flow during both an increase or decrease in ocular perfusion pressure (OPP).^[190,193]

The essential role of the VDR-GABA-eNOS-cGMP PKG signalling pathway in neuronal and cardiovascular developmental stages or ontogeny

GABAergic therapy with VDR-GABA-eNOS-cGMP-PKG signaling enhancers may be a compelling necessity in neurodevelopmental disorders and post natal behaviours. These

disorders range from childhood autism spectrum disorders, developmental language disorders (DLD) to adult diseases such as Parkinson's disease and schizoaffective disorders. GABA influences neuronal ontogeny of which consists of neuronal proliferation, migration, differentiation, KCC2/NKCC1 regulation of excitation/inhibition, axonal connectivity and neurotransmitter system development; and it may be perturbed in various neurodevelopmental diseases such as ASD and developmental language disorders.^[194] The neurosteroid-like hormone vitamin D regulates calcium homeostasis, enhances clearance of amyloid peptide, and displays antioxidant/anti-inflammatory effects vital for GABA/glutamate equilibrium and prevention of neurodegenerative processes such as glaucoma. VDR-GABA-eNOS-cGMP-PKG axis is necessary in cardiovascular ontogeny and cardiovascular homeostasis.^[195] Vitamin D is required for development of epicardial cardiomyocyte-derived cells required for proper development of the coronary circulation. It is also required in cardiac remodelling. Vitamin D-GABA-NO axis is required for maintenance of vascular health, endothelial function and prevention of atherosclerosis. The vitamin D upregulation of the vitagene nuclear factor erythroid 2-related factor 2 or Nrf2- heme oxygenase- carbon monoxide- nitric oxide pathway and downregulation of the Nrf2 inhibitor BTB and CNC homolog I (BACH1) regulates vascular and neurovascular homeostasis to prevent coronary artery disease, heart failure, hypertension, stroke and even liver or kidney failure. VDR signalling is vital for immunomodulation by inhibiting proinflammatory pathways and upregulating anti-inflammatory pathways.^[196,197,198]

Immunoregulatory functions of vitamin D3 is critical for preventing autoimmunity, infections, and immunosenescence

Vitamin D3 signalling via mVDR and nVDR plays a vital role in immunoregulation. Vitamin D3 upregulates AMPs by upregulating the functions of macrophages and monocytes in the innate immune system thereby preventing acute infections due to bacteria, viruses or fungi. It prevents excessive pro-inflammatory cytokine formation and inflammasome activation which help to tamp down chronic inflammations. For example, it downregulates TNF- α – induced upregulation of CD28^{NULL} T-cells in chronic infections and ageing. It also downregulates IL-6 which contributes to autoimmune diseases. On the other hand, vitamin D upregulates the anti-inflammatory and anti-allergic IL-10 and IL-13. Vitamin D inhibits the upregulation of the adaptive immune system by dendritic cells which are antigen-presenting cells, while it enhances the tolerogenic action of tolerogenic dendritic cells (tDCs) which increases FOXP3 T_{regs}.

Vitamin D downregulates type 1 and type 3 immunity due to t-bet and ROR γ^t receptors respectively thereby downregulating IFN-gamma and Th1/Th17-associated responses which are linked with autoimmune diseases such as relapsing-remitting multiple sclerosis, rheumatoid arthritis and Guillain-Barre syndrome; while it modulates GATA-3 of type 2 immunity to inhibit allergic responses. Deficiency of vitamin D worsens gut microbiota dysbiosis and immunosenescence and this bogey is aggravated in ageing-associated inflammaging.

In mice lacking folate receptor alpha, vitamin D enhances brain folate transfer at the BBB by enhancing significantly reduced folate carrier (RFC) functional expression which helps mitigate neurodevelopmental disorders such as autism spectrum disorders, ADHD, IQ defects, congenital defects and neurodegenerative disorders such as schizophrenia/Parkinsonism/epilepsy/hypotonia. This buttresses the assumption that vitamin D supplementation could also mitigate the consequences of folate receptor alpha (FR α) autoantibodies which is implicated in cerebral folate deficiency-induced autistic disorders or, at least, be synergistic with high-dose folinic acid (leucovorin) in this regard,^[199,205] for the reason that vitamin D provides an alternative route of folate transfer.^[206]

Small vessel disease, stroke and effect of vitamin D3 or its mimetics/synergists

In small vessel disease, there are microinfarcts in cerebral/cerebellar white matter which may be symptomless but may induce vertigo/dizziness. Small vessel disease may lead to a quarter of all stroke incidence if left unchecked. It is a major public health problem and it is associated with gait and balance disorder especially in the aged as ageing increases arteriolosclerosis-associated otoconial dislodgement- associated dizziness.^[207]

Drugs that target microvascular endothelium, the BBB, enhance BDNF, endothelial function and attenuate neuroinflammation may be more important than antiplatelets and antithrombotics in attenuating arteriolosclerosis-associated otoconial dislodgement. In this regard, vitamin D supplementation, GABA agonists which have neurotrophic role by upregulating BDNF, nitric oxide donors or upregulators, PD-5 and -3 inhibitors which upregulate cGMP, and its agonist cAMP are useful.

Vitamin D3 alone or combined with upregulators of GABA/glutamate ratio decreases small vessel disease markers such as lacunes, white matter hyperintensities and deep cerebral microbleeds. Vitamin D, GABA and resveratrol, curcumin enhance endothelial nitric oxide

by preventing its uncoupling by ROS thereby protecting the endothelium. So also is PD-5 inhibitors such as tadalafil since PD-5 is present in arterioles of subcortical white matter. Vitamin D may prevent stroke and is useful in the rehabilitation phase. So also are GABA agonists, eNOS upregulators and the phosphodiesterase – 5 inhibitor tadalafil which prevents cGMP destruction by phosphodiesterase. They may decrease infarct size and are antithrombotic, decreasing thrombomodulin, P-selectin and plasminogen activator inhibitor-I in ischaemic stroke which constitutes 87% of all strokes.^[208,217]

Vitamin D and its mimetics which include curcumin, carnosic acid, resveratrol and EGCG also are useful in post stroke recovery and rehabilitation.^[218,219]

Vitamin D and vitamin D mimetics enhance cognition

Though human studies have not shown high approval, animal experimentations mostly have indicated that vitamin D, curcumin, carnosic acid, resveratrol and EGCG enhance cognition. Bioavailability centrally may be a key determinant as most of the bioactive compounds have short half-lives.^[220,221,222]

Vitamin D and its mimetics such as carnosic acid, curcumin, EGCG and resveratrol may be complementary with low-dose lithium in cardiometabolic and neuropsychiatric disorders. Early -life administration of GABAergic enhancers such as rosemary, chamomile, turmeric, strawberries and green teas enhance cognition. So also is supplementation with vitamin D and vitamin D mimetics such as turmeric, resveratrol and EGCG use in the aged who may be vitamin D-deficient and the use of PDE-5 inhibitors such as tadalafil which enhance cGMP. They stand to over-ride the negative impact of amyloid- β on GABA, or on cGMP-CREB signalling. They can prevent A β -induced disruption of GABA and cGMP-CREB signalling and memory decline to boost cognition comparable to lithium. Enhancing GABA, as mentioned previously, increases visual-discrimination performance: enhances greater moment-to-moment signal variability in older adults comparable to that of young adults, increases complexity, flexibility, dynamic range, information transfer and stronger long-range functional connectivity predictive of increased cognitive function.^[223,224] Presently, head-to-head comparisons have shown that tadalafil displays more cognitive enhancement in humans than the GLP-I agonist semaglutide.^[225,226] In future, workers may be able to dissect the cognitive-enhancing aspect of tadalafil from the ED/LUTS attenuating aspect.

These compounds can prevent cGMP -induced endosomal uptake of amyloid precursor protein (APP) and the formation of amyloid plaques, enhance BBB A β clearance via low-density lipoprotein like receptor (LRP-I), decrease microglial activation and glutamatergic excitotoxicity. They impact positively neurotrophic factors like BDNF and CREB and SOD2, and other vitagenes. They decrease apoptosis and inflammatory and oxidative stress, enhance sirtuins and decrease inflammasome activation; and downregulate central insulin resistance.^[227,230]

Vitamin D deficiency may be linked to neurodegeneration and impaired memory and executive function in human beings and the vitamin D mimetics/synergists carnosic acid, resveratrol, curcumin and EGCG have shown benefits in slowing dementia progression. Vitamin D , its mimetics and synergist particularly resveratrol has been reported to enhance balance, memory , executive function and decrease essential tremors that may worsened by leukoencephalopathies such as cerebral autosomal dominant arteriopathy with subcortical infarcts and leukoencephalopathy (CADASIL) and other demyelination diseases such as the autoimmune multiple sclerosis (MS). Immunosuppressive treatments for MS such as fingolimod may induce JC virus infection reactivation by attenuating Lingo-I/Nogo-A/NgRI/P75/RhA/ROCK-2 pathways.^[231,232] As confirmed in our Case Reports, vitamin D and its mimetics enhance executive function, memory and resilience. Resilience is enhanced because they influence serotonin metabolism and immunoregulation. Learning performance, memory has been found to be enhanced by vitamin D and its mimetics. Patients with higher vitamin D levels have been to score better in the MMSE and Perceived Stress Scale tests.^[233,236]

Vitamin D-VDR-GABA-eNOS-cGMP axis in prevention, and treatment of neuropsychiatric diseases

Neuropsychiatric disorders such as anxiety/depression/schizophrenia/bipolar disorder/autism spectrum disorders/ADHD/neurodevelopmental diseases such as Pitt-Hopkins syndrome and West syndrome may be due to vitamin D deficiency and they can confound vertigo diagnosis. Non-vertiginous persistent postural-perceptual dizziness (PPPD) which is a chronic functional subjective and maladaptive disorder may be related to anxiety, schizoaffective disorders, migraine, BPPV, traumatic brain injury, barotrauma and dysautonomia. Vitamin D supplementation may alleviate neuropsychiatric disorders. It also attenuates anxiety- and BPPV- induced PPPD for it enhances neurexins, stabilizes perineuronal nets (PNN) in

neuronal extracellular matrix, attenuates iNOS and nNOS while it upregulates eNOS, decreases calcium signalling and decreases inflammatory cytokines to enhance synaptic plasticity/cognitive function which may be disrupted in neuropsychiatric and neurodevelopmental diseases. Moreover it increases presynaptic release of serotonin, dopamine and GABA while decreasing glutamate.^[237,240]

Additionally, enhancing GABA and cGMP levels shows benefit in the alleviation of neuropsychiatric diseases and this underlies the benefit of non-classical GABAergic enhancers and also PDE-5 inhibitors.^[241,242]

Role of the VDR-GABA-eNOS-cGMP pathway in myocardial infarction and heart failure

All the segments of the axis prevent myocardial infarction and its complications such as arrhythmias and heart failure. Vitamin D deficiency is an independent and preventable factor for myocardial infarction (MI) and infarct size following acute ST elevation myocardial infarction (STEMI). Vitamin D deficiency may increase risk and severity of myocardial infarction, slowing recovery. Vitamin D displays anti-inflammatory effects, anti-atherosclerosis effects and has positive effect on endothelial function. Vitamin D downregulates the RAAS to display anti-fibrotic, anti-inflammatory and anti-remodelling effects. Vitamin D promotes cardiac stem/progenitor cells to hasten resolution of myocardial infarct size.^[243,244] The GABA segment inhibits sympathetic hyperreactivity, effect of of ischaemia-reperfusion injury and MI-induced arrhythmias.^[245,246]

The eNOS-cGMP segment regulates coronary vasodilation, tone and contractility of cardiomyocytes. Endothelial nitric oxide and K_{ATP} interaction prevent ischaemic heart disease; preserves ejection fraction, contributes to smaller infarct sizes and inhibits the aggravating effects of I-R injury after MI. It also prevents adverse structural changes (remodelling) and apoptosis of cardiomyocytes after MI.^[247]

The cGMP functions as endothelial nitric oxide in reducing Ca^{2++} influx, reduction of preload and afterload, decreasing I-R injury and in regulating tone and contractility following MI. These functions are aided by the activation of PKG, negative regulation of GSK-3 β and protein kinase B (Akt) by protein phosphatase 2A thereby positively contributing to the regulation of cAMP-induced hypertrophy and thus prevent heart failure.^[248]

Tadalafil, the only PDE-5 inhibitor that crosses the BBB was first developed for coronary artery disease. The inhibition of cGMP phosphodiesterase by tadalafil ameliorates volume and pressure load in ischaemic heart disease. Tadalafil blunts β -adrenergic induced cardiac contractility and enhances cardiac stem cell survival. Tadalafil decreases myocardial fibrosis, apoptosis and remodelling thereby preventing heart failure. It does this by decreasing the RhoA activation for Rho-kinase. It also downregulates angiotensin II- and ET-I- induced transient receptor potential canonical 6 (TRPC6) phosphorylation to suppress non-selective Ca^{2+} ion channel conductance which leads to downregulation of Ca^{2+} -calmodulin dependent calcineurin activation and blunting of nuclear factor of activated T cells (NFAT)-induced hypertrophy. Thus, cGMP upregulation indirectly by vitamin D, phyto-derived bioactive compounds resveratrol, curcumin and apigenin and directly by tadalafil stand to prevent maladaptive remodelling and heart failure and cardiac arrhythmias.^[249,250,251]

Overlapping and synergistic role of VDR enhancers, GABAergic – endothelial nitric oxide enhancers and tadalafil in airways resistance

Cardiopulmonary diseases may be linked to vertigo/dizziness. Adequate blood and oxygen supply to the vestibular structures and brain depend on optimal cardiopulmonary function. Direct or indirect VDR enhancers such as vitamin D, curcumin, resveratrol and EGCG which also enhance GABA to endothelial nitric oxide; and the synthetic tadalafil may by their anti-oxidant and anti-inflammatory actions decrease airways tone and hyperreactivity,^[252,253] and vitamin D may increase response to steroids by upregulating glucocorticoid receptor- α and decreasing IL-17.^[254] GABA-NO dysregulation in states such as pulmonary neuroendocrine cell (PNEC) induced GABA secretion and VEGF-mucus metaplasia may counteract the useful role of NO in increasing mucociliary clearance by enhancing ciliary- beat – time frequency which helps in removal of foreign bodies from the airways, and alleviation of asthma and COPD. PNEC-derived GABA may worsen effects of mucus in cystic fibrosis caused by defective cystic fibrosis transmembrane conductance regulator (CFTR). This is antithesis to the mucus-clearing role of GABA – nitric oxide pathway induced increase in ciliary action.^[255,256]

Vitamin D enhances the production of antimicrobial peptides such as cathelicidins and defensins which helps to prevent infections in the airways. Vitamin D inhibits production of proinflammatory cytokines such as IL-2 and promotes the production of the anti-inflammatory IL-10. It also helps to prevent structural changes (remodelling) in the airways

by decreasing MMPs and ICAMI. These ensure adequate blood supply to the airways and help to prevent the adverse effects of pulmonary fibrosis, pneumoconiosis and chronic lung diseases. Tadalafil for example decreases pulmonary arterial resistance and pulmonary hypertension to enhance ventricular ejection fraction thereby increasing exercise tolerance. Vitamin D, curcumin and tadalafil are anti-fibrogenic and attenuate interstitial lung disease by inhibiting RAAS, inhibiting NF-kappaB and aberrant wnt/ β -catenin pathway and also inhibiting myofibroblast activation.^[257,258,259]

Role of the VDR-GABA-eNOS-cGMP-PKG axis in sarcopenia and musculoskeletal function

Sarcopenia is progressive loss and atrophy of skeletal muscle function. It is often associated with ageing, CKD, diabetes, sepsis, HIV/AIDS and frequently increases risks of falls in old age which confounds vertigo diagnosis. Immobility due to musculoskeletal malfunction and fractures worsen sarcopenia and can be the precipitating factor. Vitamin D or its mimetics through the VDR induces myogenic differentiation in skeletal muscle derived stem cells by upregulating the myogenic regulatory factors MyOD, MyOG, MYC2, skeletal muscle fast troponin I and T, BMP4, MMP9. Other muscle fibre factors that enhance fibre renewal are IGFI, MYHI, FGFI and II, follistatin (FST) which inhibits myostatin.^[260] Vitamin D and nitric oxide enhance Pax7 which is necessary for proliferation, self-renewal of satellite or muscle stem cells,^[261,262] and both are necessary for neuromuscular junction development. cGMP- dependent and independent pathways via Vangl2 maintain quiescent satellite cells. There is an absolute requirement for PAX7-positive satellite cells in acute injury-induced skeletal muscle regeneration.^[263] Vitamin D/VDR signalling attenuates skeletal muscle atrophy by suppressing renin-angiotensin system because the RAAS- PI3K-Akt- FOXOI pathway induces muscle atrophy.^[264] GABA or cGMP prevent age-related sarcopenic obesity in mice with high-fat-diet-induced obesity.^[265,266]

Vitamin D, the vitamin mimetics curcumin and resveratrol increase the thickness of articular cartilage and periosteal cartilage by upregulating Sox9. Similarly, tadalafil increase bone mass by upregulating VEGF, angiogenesis, vitamin D3, and bone morphogenic proteins such as myoblast determination I (MyOD). For example, curcumin attenuates environment-induced osteoarthritis by upregulating Sox9 and downregulating NF-kappaB/TGF-beta. Curcumin is thus beneficial for fracture -healing. Tadalafil may display synergistic effect with curcumin in alleviating joint destruction biomarkers of MMP-3 and RANKL and

downregulating IL-6/JAK2/STAT3 signalling pathway.^[267,277] Vitamin D, curcumin and tadalafil via cGMP also display anti-fibrotic/anti-fibrogenic effects which explains their alleviating effects in trigger finger.^[278,279] They are thus able to prevent or alleviate falls due probably to loss of muscle strength in the aged, a key element in the vertigo dizziness syndrome of the aged.

The gut-joint axis and the gut-brain axis

Apart from contributing to boost non-pathogenic bacteria and decreasing periodontopathogens in the oral microbiome, thereby attenuating periodontitis-related eNOS uncoupling, vitamin D boosts probiotic bacteria including Akkermansia and Bifidobacteria; and modulates enterotypes-distinct patterns of gut microbiota composition; enhancing the benefits of probiotics and prebiotics for stroke and coronary heart disease. *Streptococcus thermophilus* and *Lactobacillus pentosus* enhance GABA production in the gut. GABA from the gut may thus upregulate Sox9 and decrease Runx and MMP9 in the joints to ameliorate osteoarthritis.^[280,281,282]

In the gut-brain axis, GABA produced in the gut and enhanced by both vitamin D and metformin is a potential mediator of important modulating functions.^[283,286] Thus vitamin D, vitamin D mimetics such as curcumin, carnolic acid, resveratrol and EGCG in conjunction with metformin may indirectly downregulate corisin, imidazole propionate, D-lactate and trimethylamine N-oxide (TMAO) implicated in chronic kidney fibrosis, diabetes-induced silent atherosclerosis, platelet hyperreactivity and thrombosis, immune dysregulation and fatty liver disease. Gut microbiota dysbiosis is also implicated in neurodegenerative diseases such as Alzheimer's disease and Parkinson's disease.^[287,291] Nitric oxide regulates skeletal muscle fatigue, fibre type, microtubule organization and mitochondrial ATP synthesis efficiently through cGMP-dependent mechanisms.^[292] Duchenne muscle dystrophy cases have an impaired NO-cGMP signalling. Phosphodiesterase-5 inhibition in skeletal muscle increases muscle contractility, increases vascular function, enhances myogenic regulatory factors such as myoblast determination protein (MyoD), slows fibrosis and decreases inflammation. Tadalafil improves lean body mass and endothelial function in non-obese men with mild LUTS.^[293,294]

The vitamin D, vitamin D mimetics/GABA/eNOS/cGMP axis role in protecting against cancer; and impacting positively regenerative medicine research

Cancer may be an unknown cause of frailty in the aged. Vitamin D and its mimetics decrease aberrant β -catenin/wnt signalling leading to the downregulation of cyclin DI and c-MyC but upregulate IGFII binding protein in rats. It may downregulate aberrant β -catenin/wnt/Notch I/Hedgehog/Hippo/NF- κ B to TGF- β important in EMT and carcinogenesis. Recently, researchers have shown that in people with normal transient receptor potential cation channel subfamily M member 7 (TRPM7) functional regulation of magnesium transport into cells (magnesium homeostasis), or magnesium supplementation increases abundance of *Carnobacterium maltaromaticum* and *Faecalibacterium prausnitzii* which increases *de novo* gut synthesis of vitamin D to inhibit colorectal carcinogenesis in female mice; and also for attenuation of metabolic syndrome, depression, IBS and inflammatory bowel disease.^[295] Periodontitis-associated expansion of gut-translocating oral pathobionts (resident commensals) such as *Haemophilus parainfluenzae* strains, *Porphyromonas gingivalis*, *Parvimonas micra*, and *Fusobacterium nucleatum* may also contribute to CRC development and expansion.^[296]

Additionally, vitamin D, its mimetics such as carnosic acid, curcumin and quercetin and also paterholides in chamomile inhibit cancer stem cells and also represses bone morphogenic protein 3 (BMP3) promoter methylation, inhibits the secondary bile acid lithocolic acid and thus not only inhibits the growth of many solid tumors such as breast, prostate, but also disturbs gastric and intestinal cancer progression.^[297,301] Vitamin D also controls cell cycle, regulates microRNAs and prevents drug resistance to be invaluable in cancer prevention and treatment.

While vitamin D3 inhibit the growth of certain germline malignancies, it can promote the bone-forming differentiation of induced pluripotent stem cells and mesenchymal cells and enhance the regeneration of the colonic lining, improving mouse colitis histology index (MCHI).^[302] It increases activation of neural stem cells to form oligodendrocytes necessary for mitigation of neurological diseases. Additionally, vitamin D3 induces activation also of cardiac stem cells by promoting mesenchymal- to- endothelial (MEndoT) transition important for vascular repair through the wnt and sonic hedgehog signalling.^[303,304] Active work is ongoing in this area of using vitamin D3 in regenerative medicine.

GABA has a controversial role presently in cancer. Upregulating GABA_ARs as add-on treatment may be useful in management of medulloblastomas or gliomas,^[305] while enhancing GABA_BR signaling may be a new method of treatment and prevention of pancreatic ductal carcinoma which has high mortality rate because it may grow insidiously.^[306]

There is also a controversial role for nitric oxide in cancer therapy.^[307,308] Loss of the nitric oxide receptor soluble guanylyl cyclase (sGC) can be used as a biomarker for aggressive tumours and NO-cGMP overexpression suppress breast, ovarian and prostate cancers and nitric oxide + ionizing radiation lead to apoptosis of colon cancerous cells.

Soluble guanylyl cyclase (sGC) and cGMP cause apoptosis in many cancers by attenuating VEGF and ERK_{1/2} signalling for sGC may decrease epithelial-to-mesenchymal transition which may be first step in cancer progression especially human endometrial and cervical cancer cells.^[309,310] Workers reported that the clinical agonist of sGC, riociguat increases the sensitivity of castration-resistant prostate cancer to chemotherapy with androgen deprivation regimens.^[311]

Tadalafil which is a cGMP potentiator inhibits purine arginine methyltransferase-5 (PRMT5) and renders colorectal cancer cells sensitive to 5-fluorouracil; and is being assessed for inclusion in management regimens for chronic lymphatic leukemic, and cancers of the prostate, colorectal, brain, breast, liver, head and neck and multiple myeloma.^[312,313]

Effect of vitamin D3 on pluripotent stem cells

Investigators have shown that vitamin D is capable of stimulating both embryonic and induced pluripotent stem cells (iPSCs) to impact the earliest stages of development in organs; and can activate the proliferation and differentiation of adult stem cells such as bone marrow mesenchymal stem cells. Vitamin D can increase the expression of markers that are indicative of a pluripotent state such as the transcription factors OCT-4, NANOG and SOX2 which maintains the stemness of embryonic stem cells, partly through SIRT1-FoxO3 signalling which reduced β -galactosidase positive cells.^[314] Apart from improving mouse colitis histology index, promoting neurogenesis and the differentiation of pluripotent stem cells into various neural cell types such as oligodendrocytes, vitamin D3 supplementation can increase the migratory and proliferative capacity of endothelial progenitor cells (EPCs), which are essential for repairing damaged blood vessels.^[315,316]

Anti-ageing effect of the VDR to cGMP axis

Elements of the vitamin D, vitamin D mimetics/GABAergic/eNOS/cGC/cGMP/PKG axis commonly display antioxidant and anti-inflammatory effects in several experimental and clinical paradigms. They enhance the functions of the critical antioxidant vitagene Nfr2 and enhance NAD⁺ and mRNA expression genes while attenuating p38 MAPK and p16.^[317] Workers have questioned commonalities between normal aging and Hutchinson-Gilford progeria syndrome (HGPS) as vitamin D/resveratrol/curcumin/quercetin supplementation attenuates HGPS, aging and aging-associated diseases such as type 2 diabetes. Progerin induces VDR defects and decreases the critical vitagenes as well as eNOS important for mechanotransduction in arteries; while vitamin D3 reduces progerin levels. Vitamin D receptor signalling improves HGPS cellular phenotypes, stabilizing breast cancer antigen 1 (BRCA1) and p53-binding protein-1 (53BP1) crucial for genome integrity. Klotho-fibroblast growth factor 23 (FGF 23) axis is downstream of progerin expression and alpha-klotho deficiency has been termed as one of the progeroid syndromes.^[318,319,320]

Lipotoxicity which plays a key role in the development of insulin resistance and muscle atrophy in type 2 diabetic patients is attenuated by exercise, and vitamin D and its mimetics which signal to PPAR-alpha. Vitamin D and its mimetics promote mitochondrial health which offsets sarcopenias and decrease senescence-associated secretory phenotype (SASP) and enhance eNOS vital for insulin signalling, endothelial function and cellular resilience. Vitamin D supplementation may slow down Hovarth epigenetic aging clock accelerated by allostatic load driven by environmental stressors.^[321] Elements of the axis stabilize DNA, attenuate telomere attrition, increase telomere length, enhance insulin signaling, enhance DNA repair and mitochondrial biogenesis; and stand to over-ride the negative effects of some environmental agents such as pollution, high processed meat/ dietary fibre ratio or even instant coffee on telomere length.^[322] Vitamin D and its phyto-derived mimetics inhibit fibrosis which is a problem with ageing and inhibit collagen degradation; while enhancing the integrity of the intestinal membrane barrier, blood-brain-barrier; and skin epithelial barrier via inhibiting ROS-MMPs- TGF- β culprit mechanisms involved in collagen breakdown and decreased elasticity in skin ageing.^[323,332]

The cGMP potentiator tadalafil which displays complementary effects with vitamin D reduces pulmonary artery pressure; enhances working memory and reduces hippocampal

oxidative stress. It downregulates ageing-associated arteriolosclerosis and its counterpart atherosclerosis.^[333,334,335]

Anti-fibrotic effect of Vitamin D, vitamin mimetics-VDR-GABA-eNOS-cGMP axis

It is recognized that fibrosis may be associated with congenital/genetic lesions such as Ehler-Danlos syndrome or Marfan syndrome, and acquired or idiopathic lesions such as Peyronie's disease, adhesive capsulitis, Dupuytren's contracture and stenosing tenosynovitis (trigger finger).

Ageing associated increase in SASP contributes to inflammaging which intersects with diabetes mellitus, CKD, RAAS overactivity, ROS-and RCS-induced advanced glycation end-products and lipid peroxidation end-products to influence TGF-beta, the master regulator of fibrosis.

Aberrant β -catenin/wnt/hedgehog/Notch/Hippo signalings could confound the pernicious role of angiotensin-II, ROS and RCS in upregulating TGF-beta-induced EMT and fibrosis via the nuclear import of Mothers against Decapentaplegic (SMAD 2/3/4). TGF-beta-SMAD 2/3/4 induces fibrosis in various organs such as heart (associated with cardiomyopathies), kidneys, lungs (idiopathic pulmonary fibrosis), abdomen (idiopathic retroperitoneal fibrosis) or even be associated with osteoarthritis-related synovial fibrosis of the various joints. In the liver there is activation of hepatic stellate cells by viruses, toxins, obesity to promote fibrosis via dysregulated NF-kappa β , TGF- β , and PI3/Akt/mTOR pathways which can aggravate to carcinoma. Vitamin D or its mimetics such as curcumin-/resveratrol-/EGCG-induced suppression of fibrosis is potentiated by cGMP potentiators such as tadalafil or vardenafil and stand to ameliorate fibrotic disorders which is associated with frailty in the aged and confounds vertigo diagnosis/management.^[336,342]

Vitamin D mimetics or synergists -VDR-GABA-eNOS-cGC-cGMP pathway enhance UCPs I/II for cold adaptation

Dietary vitamin D or its mimetics/synergists decrease obesity, enhance lean body mass, decrease visceral adipose tissue, enhance mitochondrial biogenesis and insulin signalling to PPARs/PGC-1 α . It also signals to enhance uncoupling protein-I (UCPI) peripherally or UCP2 centrally. The pathway thus enhances non-shivering thermogenesis with concomitant attenuation of ROS centrally via AMPK activation.^[343,344]

GABAergic signalling has anti-obesity effects via enhanced PKA, UCPI and eNOS /Sirtuins pathways.^[345,346] While the cGMP potentiator tadalafil serves to promote preadipocytes towards a metabolically healthy phenotype via decreasing inflammatory cytokines and enhancing adiponectin and UCPI. Tadalafil with synergistic involvement of gut microbiota potentiates the other elements of the axis to enhance beiging or browning of white adipose tissue, enhancing its thermogenic BAT phenotype necessary for increased cold adaptation and obesity management. Tadalafil also enhances blood flow and function in skeletal muscle while decreasing pain to attenuate chronic cold Complex Regional Pain Syndrome (CRPS) and this also contributes to cold adaptation.^[347]

The gut-microbiome-adipose axis as well as the gut microbiota-miR-181 axis controlled by tryptophan metabolites are disrupted in obesity and insulin resistance and can be rescued by appropriate nutrients containing vitamin D /vitamin D mimetics or synergists/prebiotics/probiotics and appropriate exercise.^[348,349,350]

CONCLUSION

Thesis of this article is that the VDR-GABA-eNOS-cGMP-PKG pathway which is upregulated by vitamin D3 or its mimetics, the phyto-derived bioactive agents turmeric-derived curcumin, strawberry-derived resveratrol/melatonin/quercetin, rosemary-derived carnosic acid, green tea-derived vitamin D synergist EGCG or even the synergist tadalafil (a cGMP potentiator) is a survival pathway. Vitamin D3 and these phyto-derived vitamin D3 mimetics/synergists also directly or indirectly enhance the non-addictive non-classical GABAergic signalling pathway and are beneficial for treatment of central/peripheral vertigo and may qualify as a new category of drugs for vertigo treatment.

The benefits of the pathway cut across not only neurodevelopmental, neurodegenerative and neuropsychiatric disorders. The advantages also extend to immunoregulatory disorders, hypertension/metabolic syndrome cluster, oncologic disorders, ageing, musculo-skeletal diseases, vision defects, infections and gut microbiome- brain axis dyshomeostasis.

It is for the significant impact of this pathway in brain-organ communication- dependent whole body- homeostasis that efforts should be directed to seeking for more herbs or phyto-derived bioactive compounds with these uses in our local environments in Nigeria.

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REFERENCES

1. Hogue J. D. "Office evaluation of dizziness". *Prim. Care: Clins. Off. Pract.* 2015; 42(2): 249-258. Doi:10.1016/j.pop.2015.01.004
2. De Joode L. E. G. H.; Martin E. C.; Stultiens J. J. A. The DizzyQuest: to have or not to have... a vertigo attack. *J. Neurol.* 2020; 267(SI): 15-23.
3. Wassif G. A., Alrehely M. S., Alharbi D. M., Aljohan A. A. The impact of vitamin D on neuropsychiatric disorders. *Cureus.* 2023; 15(10): e47716
4. Irwin J. Synopsis of causation of vertigo. Gov.UK. 2008; [https://assets publishing services.gov.uk](https://assets.publishing.services.gov.uk).
5. Staab J. P., Ruckenstein M. J. Expanding the differential diagnosis of chronic dizziness. *Arch. Otolaryngol. Head Neck Surg.* 2007; 133(2): 170-176. Doi: 10.1001/archotol.133.2.170.
6. Sogebi O. A., Ariba A, J., Oulana T. O., Osalusi B. A. Vestibular disorders in elderly patients: Characteristics, causes and consequences. *Pan Afr. Med. J.*, 2014; 19: doi: 10.11604/pamj. 2014; 19: 146.3146.
7. Osuji A. E. The interaction of hypertension for vertigo in audio-vestibular medicine clinic. *J. Res Vest. SC.*, 2022; 21(22): 29-39.
8. McCullough P. J., Lehrer D. S., Amend J. Daily oral dosing of vitamin D3 using 5000 to 50,000 international units a day in long-term hospitalized patients: Insights from a seven year experience. *The J. Ster. Biochem. Mol. Biol.* 2019; 189: 228-239. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jsbmb.2018.12.010>
9. Dai Q., Zhu X., Manson J. E., Song Y., Li X., Franke A. Bimodal relationship between magnesium supplementation and vitamin D status and metabolism: Results from a randomized trial [abstract]. *Proc. Am. Assoc. Canc. Res. Ann. Meet. Chicago.* 2018; 78(13 Suppl): Abst. Nr CT093.
10. Shahsavani Z., Asadi A., H., Shamsheirgardi E., Akbarzadeh M. Vitamin D, magnesium and their interactions: A review. *Int. J. Nutr. Sci.* 2021; 6(3): 113-118. Doi: 10.30476/IJNS.2021.91766.1144.

11. Kirkland A. E., Sarlo G. L., Holton K. The role of magnesium in neurological disorders. *Nutrient*. 2018; 10(6): 730 doi: 10.3390/nu10060730.
12. Kostov K. Effects of magnesium deficiency on mechanisms of insulin resistance in T2D: Focusing on the processes of insulin secretion and signalling. *IJMS*. 2019; 20(6): 1351. Doi: 10.3390/ijms20061351.
13. Arabnezhad L., Mohammadifard M., Rahmani L., Majidi Z., Ferns G. A., Bahrami A. Effects of curcumin supplementation on vitamin D levels in women with premenstrual syndrome and dysmenorrhea: A randomized controlled study. *BMC Complement. Med Ther*. 2022; 22: 19. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12906-022-03515-2>.
14. Stone D. A., Batie S. F., Sabir M. S., Jacobs E. T., Lee J. H., Whitfield G. K., Haussler M. R. . Resveratrol potentiates vitamin D and nuclear receptor signaling. *J. Cell Biochem*. 2015; 16(6): 1130-43.
15. Haussler M. R., Haussler C. A., Bartik L., Whitfield G. K., Hsieh H., Slater S. Vitamin D receptor: Molecular signaling and activities of nutritional ligands in disease prevention. *Nutr. Rev*. 2009; 66(10S2): S98-112. Doi: 10.1111/j.1753-4887.2008.00093.x.
16. Kattah J. C., Talkad A. V., Wang D. Z., Hsieh Y-H., Newman-Toker D. E. HINTS to diagnose stroke in the acute vestibular syndrome: Three- step bedside oculomotor examination more sensitive than early MRI diffusion-weighted imaging. *Strok*. 2019; 40(11). Doi: 10.1161/STROKEAHA.109.551234.
17. Kim J-S., Newman-Toker D. E., Kerber K. A., Jahn K., Bertholon P., Waterston J. E. Consensus document of the committee for the classification of vestibular disorders of the Barany Society. 2022; 32(3): 205-222.
18. Jia Q., Zha Z., Li S., Zhang Y., Ke L., Liu S. Genetic and mendelian randomization analyses support causal relationships between instant coffee and age-related macular degeneration. *Food Sci. Nutr*. 2025; 13(6): e70439. Doi: 10.1002/fsn3.70439.
19. Matachione G., Gurau F., Silvestrini A. Anti-SASP and anti-inflammatory activity of resveratrol, curcumin and β -caryophyllene association on human endothelial and monocytic cells. *Biogerontol*. 2021; 22: 297-313.
20. Ajitkumar A., Mohan G., Ghose M., Yarrarapu S., Afiniwala S. Drug-induced liver injury secondary to turmeric use. *Eur. J. Rep. Int. Med*. 2023; 21: 10(5): doi: 10.12890/2023.003845.
21. Markus H. S., van der Worp H. S., Rothwell P. M. Posterior circulation ischaemic stroke and TIA: Diagnosis, investigation and secondary prevention. *The Lanc. Neurol*. 2013; 12(10): 989-998.

22. Arun P. T., Kumar R. S. C., Narang S. The relationship between hypertension and vertigo: A comparative study. *J. Nov. RES. Inno. Dev.* 2025; 3(2): JNRID: 2507016.
23. Song S-H., Shin D. H., Her Y. S., Oh M. H., Baek J. W., Sung S. Effect of PDE-inhibitors on sperm motility and acrosome reaction: An *in vitro* study. *Invest. Clin. Urol.* 2021; 62(3): 354-350.
24. Greco E. A., Antinozzi C., Di Luigi L., Aversa A. Tadalafil and steroid hormones interactions in adipose, bone and prostate tissues: Focus on translational perspectives. *IJMS.* 2022; 23(8): 4191; <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijms2308191>
25. Alp H. H., Huyut Z., Yildirim S., Basbugan Y., Ediz L., Sekeroglu M. R. The effect of PDE-5 inhibitors on bone and oxidative damage in ovariectomy-induced osteoporosis. *Exp. Biol. Med (Maywood).* 2017; 24(10): 1051-1061. Doi: 10.1177/1535370217703352.
26. Bonilla C., Ness A. R., Willis A. K., Lawlor D. A., Lewis S. J. Skin pigmentation, sun exposure and vitamin D levels in children of the Avon Longitudinal Study of parents and children. *BMC Publ. Health.* 2014; 14: 597. Doi: 10.1186/1471-2458-14-597.
27. Liu X-a., Li X., Shen P., Cong B., Wang L. Fundamental role of brain-organ interaction in behaviour-driven holistic homeostasis. *Fund. Res.* 2024; <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fmre.2024.09.005>.
28. Wang J., Huang H., Liu C., Zheng Y., Wang W. Research progress on the role of vitamin D in autism spectrum disorder. *Front. Behavior. Neurosc.* 2022; 16: 859151.
29. Kasalkina L. A., Tarasenko A. S., Krupko O. O., Kuchmerovska T. M., Lisakovska O. O. Vitamin D deficiency induces the excitation/inhibition brain imbalance and the pro-inflammatory shift. *The Internat. J. Biochem. Cell. Biol.* 2020; 119: 105665.
30. Sen S., Roy S., Bendyopadhyasy G., Scott B., Ramadoss S., Mahata S. K. GABA is synthesized and released by the endothelium: Potential implications. *Circ. Res.* 2016; 119(5). <https://doi.org/10.1161/CIRCRESAHA.116.308645>.
31. Li S., Kumar T. P., Joshee S., Khalili J. S., Kloepper J., Du C. Endothelial cell-derived GABA signaling modulates neuronal migration and post-natal behaviors. *Cell Res.* 2018; 28(2): 221-248. Doi: 1038/cr.2017.135.
32. Negri S., Scolari F., Vismara M., Btrunetti V., Faris P. GABA-A and GABA-B receptors mediate GABA-induced intracellular Ca²⁺ signals in human brain microvascular endothelial cells. *Cells.* 2022; 11(23): <https://10.3390/cells/11233860>.
33. Cherubini E., Ben-Ari Y. GABA signaling: Therapeutic targets for neurodegenerative and neurodevelopmental disorders. *Br. SC.* 2023; 13(9): 10.3390/brainsci.13091240.

34. Reyes-Harpo D., Cisneros-Mejorado A., Arellano R. O. Therapeutic potential of GABAergic signaling in myelin plasticity and repair. *Front. Cell Dev. Biol.* 2023; <https://doi.org/10.3389/cell.2021.662191>.
35. Petrovic M., Pavlovic D., Palmer Z., Udo S. B., Citadin C. T., Rodgers K. M. Modulation of GABAergic system as a therapeutic option in stroke. *Expt. Neurol.* 2025; 384: 115050.
36. Kowalowka M., Goma I., Karazniewicz-Lada M., Kusyk D., Przyslawski J., Drzymala-Czyz S. Nutri-epigenetic regulation of vitamin D- Impact on metabolism and biological functions: Narrative review. *Metabolit.* 2025; 15(7): 436, <https://doi.org/10.3390/metabo15070436>.
37. Zhang F., Guo X., Xia Y., Mao L An update on the phenotypic switching of VSMCs in the pathogenesis of atherosclerosis. *Cell Mol. Lif. Sci.* 2021; 79(1): 6 doi: 10.1007/s00018-021-04079-z.
38. Frismantiene A., Philippova M., Erne P., Resink T. J. Smooth muscle cell-driven vascular diseases and molecular mechanisms of VSMC plasticity. *Cellul. Signall.* 2018; 52; 48-64 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cellsig.2018.08.019>.
39. Sun S. W., Tong W. J., Guo Z. F., Tuo Q. H., Lei X. Y., Zhang C. P. Curcumin enhances vascular contractility via induction of myocardin in VSMCs. *Acta Pharmacol. Sin.* 2017; 38(10): 1329-1339.
40. Duddu S., Chakrabarti R., Shukla P. Vitamin D attenuates PCSK9-orchestrated phenotypic switch of vascular smooth muscle cells. *Atheroscler.* 2024; 395(SI): 117644.
41. Hepsomali P., Groeger J. A., Nishihira J., Scholey A. Effects of oral GABA administration on stress and sleep in humans; A systematic review. *Front. Neurosc.* 2020; 14: 923.
42. Nishiyama M., Togashi K., Aihara T., Hong K. GABAergic activities control spike-timing and frequency-dependent long-term depression at hippocampal excitatory synapses. *Front. Synap. Neurosc.* 2010; 2-2010/<https://doi.org/10.3389/fnsyn.2010.00222>.
43. Xiang Z., Huguenard J., Prince D, A. GABA-A receptor-mediated-currents in interneurons of pyramidal cells of rat visual cortex. *J. Physiol.* 1998; 506(3): 715-730.
44. Song C., Sandberg K., Andersen L. M., Blicher J., Rees G. Human occipital and parietal GABA selectively influence visual perception of orientation and size. *J. Neurosc.* 2017; 37(37): 8929-8937.
45. Micarelli A., Granito I., Micarelli R. X., Alessandrini M. The impact of hypertension and related risk factors on the onset and resolution rate of BPPV recurrence: A 6-year retrospective study. *Neurol. Int.* 2025; 17(6): 82.

46. Oriaifo S. E. O., Omonkhafé A. A., Ohaju-Obodo J. O. Pharmacovigilance: Tiens-slimming tea causes increased blood pressure. *WJ Pharma. Drug Res.* 2007; 22(23): 39-41.
47. Mahmud A., Feely J. Acute effect of caffeine on arterial stiffness and aortic pressure waveform. *Hypertens.* 2001; 38(2). <https://doi.org/10.1161/01.HYP.38.2.22420>.
48. Staikoglou N., Polanagnostaki A., Lamprou E., Charlam pilas E., Pavlou E. Posterior cerebral artery disease after excessive caffeine consumption in a teenager. *Radiol. Cms. Rep.* 2022; 17(6): 281-284.
49. Gaspar C., Rocha C., Balteiro J., Santas N. Effect of caffeine on cerebral blood flow. *Nutr.* 2024; 20(23): <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nuty.2023.112217>.
50. Ahmad T., Masenga S. K., Kleyman T. R., Ertuglu L. A., Kirabo A. The epithelial sodium channel in inflammation and blood pressure modulation. *Front. Cardiovasc. Med.* 2023; 10. 2023/<https://doi.org/10.3389/cvm.2023-1130148>.
51. Xiao L., Patrick D.M., Aden L. A., Kiraba A. Mechanism of isolevuglandins protein adduct formation in inflammation and hypertension. *Lipid Media.* 2018; 139: 48-53.
52. Govindarajan B., Junk A., Algeciras M., Salomon R. C., Bhattacharyas S. K. Increased isolevuglandins-modified proteins in glaucomatous astrocytes. *Mol. Vis.* 2009; 15: 1079-91.
53. Govindarajan B., Laird J., Salomon R. C., Bhattacharya S. R. Isolevuglandin-modified proteins including elevated levels of inactive calpain-I accumulate in glaucomatous trabecular meshwork. *Biochem.* 2007; 47(2): 817-825.
54. Akkina S. K., Ricardo A., Patel A., Das A., Bazzano L. A. Illicit drug use, hypertension and chronic kidney disease in the US adult population. *Transl. Res.* 2012; 160(6): 391-398.
55. Sun M., Wu C., Liu X., Gu L., Wang R. Interplay between RAAS and oxidative stress contributes to alcohol addiction by stimulating dopamine accumulation in the mesolimbic pathway. *Biochem. Pharmacol.* 2023; 212: 115578.
56. Kovacic P. Unifying mechanism for addiction and toxicity of abused drugs with application to dopamine and glutamate mediators: Election transfer and ROS. *Med. Hypothes.* 2025; 65(1): 90-6
57. Soltaninejad M., Amlashi R. S., Shalami M., Shabani M. Unravelling the protective effects of curcumin against drugs of abuse. *Heliyon.* 2024; 10(9): e30468

58. Dharavath R. N., Pina-Leblanc M., Tang V. M., Sloan M. E., Nikolava Y. S. GABAergic signaling in alcohol use disorder and withdrawal: pathological involvement and therapeutic potential. *Front. Neurol. Circ.* 2023; 17: 1218737.
59. Lychenvik T., Woock M., Johansson K., Axelsson M., Zetterberg H. Cerebrospinal fluid biomarkers in opioid dependence: Evidence of neuro-immune activation and ion composition changes, without alteration in orexin-A. *Addict Biol.* 2025; 30(6): e70053.
60. Jolilian-Khave L., Kitameh R., Ysrayi B. B., Borelli A., Punaro M. C. Potential role for vitamin D in preventing and treating impulse disorders, behavioral addictions, and substance use disorders: A scoping review. *Addict. Neurosci.* 2025; 14: 100190.
61. Lin C., Kong Y., Chen Q., Zeng J., Pan X. Decoding STREM2: Its impact on Alzheimer's disease: A comprehensive review of mechanisms and implications. *Front. Aging Neurosci.* 2024; 16: 1420731.
62. Akbari M., Parsael H., Sedaghat K., Mousari F. Attenuation of morphine place preference and reinstatement by vitamin D. *Beh. Pharmacol.* 2023; 34(7): 404-410.
63. Jouvert P., Revel M-O., Lazaris A., Aunis D., Langley K. Activation of the cGMP pathway in dopaminergic structures reduces cocaine-induced EGR-I expression and locomotor activity. *J. Neurosci.* 2004; 24(47): 10716-10725.
64. Wen R-T., Zhang F-F., Zhang H-T. Cyclic nucleotide phosphodiesterases: Potential therapeutic targets for alcohol use disorders. *Psychopharmacol (Berl.)*. 2018; 235(6): 1793-1805.
65. Choi M., Ozeki J., Hashizume M., Kato S., Ishihara H. Vitamin D receptor activation induces peptide YY transcription in pancreatic islets. *Endocrinol.* 2012; 153: 5188-99.
66. Abbas M. A. Physiological function of vitamin D in adipose tissue. *Steroid Biochem. Mol. Biol.* 2017; 165(Part 13): 369-381. Doi: 10.1016/j.jsbmb.2016.08.004.
67. Sheikholeslami-Vatani D., Rostamzadeh N. Changes in appetite-dependent hormones and body composition after 8 weeks of high-intensity interval training and vitamin D supplementation in sedentary overweight men. *Front. Nutr.* 2022; 9: 82763.
68. Ajabshir S., Asif A., Nayer A. The effects of vitamin D on the renin-angiotensin system. *J. Nephropath.* 2014; 3(2): 41-43. Doi: 10.12860/jnp.2014.09.
69. Turkes G. F., Uysal S., Dmir T., Demiral Y., Pamuk B. O. Association between vitamin D and remnant cholesterol in patients with T2DM. *Cureus.* 2021; 13(2): e13248.
70. Mann M. C., Hollenberg M. D., Hanley D. A., Ahmed S. B. Vitamin D, the ANS, and cardiovascular risk. *Physiol. Rev.* 2015; 3(4): e12349. <https://doi.org/10.14814/phy2.12349>.

71. Zovi A., Ferrara F., Pasquinucci R., Nava L., Vitiello A., Arrigoni R., Ballini A. Effects of vitamin D on RAS and acute childhood pneumonia. *Antibiot (Basel)*. 2022; 11(11): 1545. Doi: 10.3390/antibiotics.1111545.
72. Amer F., El-rehany M., Ali O. Combination therapy with vitamin D and telmisartan to suppress the progression of liver fibrosis. *J. Med. Lif. Sci.* 2024; 6(2): 132-143. <https://jmals.journals.ekb.eg/>.
73. Roizen J. D., Long C., Casella A., O'Lear L., Caplan I., Lai M. Obesity decreases hepatic 25-hydroxylase activity causing low serum 25-hydroxyvitamin D. *J. Bone Min. Res.* 2019; 34(6): 1068-1073. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jbmr.3686>.
74. Nimitphong H., Saetung S., Chailurkit L., Chanprasertyothin S., Ongphiphadhanakul B. Vitamin D supplementation is associated with serum uric acid concentration in patients with prediabetes and hyperuricemia. *J. Clin. Transl. Endocrinol.* 2021; 24: 100255. Doi: 10.1016/j.jcte.2021.100255.
75. Unger T., Bles F., Gantem D., Lang R. E., Rettig R. GABAergic stimulation inhibits central actions of angiotensin II: Pressor responses, drinking and release of vasopressin. *Eur. J. Pharmacol.* 1983; 90(1): 1-9.
76. Gul R., Alsalman A., Alfadda A. A. Inhibition of eNOS practically blunts the beneficial effects of angiotensin II-induced signalling in H9c2 cardiomyocytes. *Curr. Iss. Mol. Biol.* 2022; 44(5): 2139-2152.
77. Engin E. GABA_A receptor subtypes and benzodiazepine use, misuse, and abuse. *Front. Psychiatr.* 2025; 13: 1060949.
78. Mergia E., Stegbauer J. Role of PDE-5 and cGMP in hypertension. *Curtr. Hypertens. Rep.* 2016; 18(5); 39.
79. Johnston G. A. R., Beart P. M. Milestone review: GABA, from chemistry, conformations, ionotropic receptors, modulators, epilepsy, flavonoids, and stress to neuro-nutraceuticals. *J. Biochem.* 2024; 168(7): 1179-1190.
80. Yue Z-J., Xe P-T., Jiao B., Chang H., Song H. Nitric oxide protects L-type calcium channel of cardiomyocyte during long-term isoproterenol stimulation in tail-suspension test. *Biomed. Res. Int.* 2015; 22; 780814.
81. Brewer L. D., Thibault V., Chen K. C., Langub M. C., Langfield P. W. Vitamin D hormone confers neuroprotection in parallel with downregulation of L-type calcium channel expression in hippocampal neurons. *Neurosc.* 2001; 21(1): 98-108.
82. Shen K., Johnson D. W., Gobe G. C. The role of cGMP and its signaling in kidney disease. *Transl. Physiol.* 2016; *Ajprenal*.00042.

83. Lau W. L., Leaf E. M., Hu M. C., Kuro-o ., Moe O. W., Giachelli C. M. Vitamin D receptor agonists increase klotho and osteopontin while decreasing aortic calcification in mice with chronic kidney disease fed a high phosphate diet. *Kidney Int.* 2012; 82(12): 1261-1270.
84. Thiel A., Hermanns C., Lauer A. A., Reichrath J., Erhardt T., Hartmann T. Vitamin D and its analogues: From differences in molecular mechanisms to potential benefits of adapted use in the treatment of Alzheimer's disease. *Nutri.* 2023; 15(7): 1684. <https://doi.org/10.3390/nu15071684>.
85. Tomita N., Hotta Y., Naiki-Ito A., Hirano K., Kataoka T., Maeda Y. The PDE-5 inhibitor tadalafil has renoprotective effects in a rat model of CKD. *Physiol. Reps.* 2020; 8(17): e4556. <https://doi.org/10.14814/phy2.14556>.
86. Stadt M., Layton H. T. Modulation of blood pressure by dietary potassium and sodium: Sex differences and modelling analysis. *AJP (Renal).* 2025; <https://doi.org/10.1152/ajprenal.0222.2024>
87. Haussler M. R., Haussler C. A., Whitfield G. K., Hsieh J-C., Thompson P.D. The nuclear vitamin D receptor controls the expression of genes encoding factors which feed 'the fountain of youth' to mediate healthful aging. *Mol. Biol.* 2010; 121(1-2): 88-97.
88. Savkur R. S., Bramlett K. S., Stayrook K. R., Nagpal S., Burns T. P. Coactivation of the human vitamin D receptor by the peroxisome proliferator-activated receptor gamma coactivator-I alpha. *Mol. Pharmacol.* 2005; 68(2): 511-517.
89. Borissova A. M., Tankova T., Kirilov G., Dakovska L., Kovacheva R. The effect of vitamin D3 on insulin secretion and peripheral insulin sensitivity in T2D patients. *Int. J. Clin. Pract.* 2003; 57(4): 258-66.
90. Argano C., Mirarchi L., Amodeo S., Orlando V., Torres A. The role of vitamin D and its molecular bases in insulin resistance diabetes, metabolic syndrome, and cardiovascular diseases: State of the art. *IJMS.* 2023; 24(30): 15485.
91. Kanter E. J., Bornfeldt K. E. Evidence stacks up that endothelial insulin resistance is a culprit in atherosclerosis. *Circ. Res.* 2013; 13(4): 113.301998.
92. Bansal P., Wang S., Liu S., Xiang Y-Y., Lu W-Y. GABA coordinates with insulin in regulating function in the pancreatic INS-I β -cells. *PLOS One* . 2011; 6(10): e26225.
93. Soltani N., Qiu H., Aleksic M., Glinka Y., Zhao F. GABA exerts protective and regenerative effect on islet beta-cell and reverses diabetes. *PNAS-USA.* 2011; 108(28): 11692-7.

94. Liu Y., Zhang Y., Hu M., Li Y-H., Cao X-H. Carnosic acid alleviates brain injury through NF-kappaB-regulated inflammation and caspase-3-associated apoptosis in high fat-induced mouse models. *Mol. Med. Repts.* 20(1): 2019; 495-504. <https://doi.org/10.3892/mmr.2019.10299>.
95. Tsuda T. Anthocyanins and curcumin; Possible abilities of prevention of diabetes and obesity via stimulation of GLP-I secretion and induction of beige adipocyte formation. *J. Nutr. Sci. Vitamin. (Tokyo)*. 2022; 68(Suppl): S110-S112.
96. Traub S., Meier D. T., Schulze F., Dror E., Nordmann T. M., Goetz N. Pancreatic alpha-cell-derived glucagon-related peptides are required for beta-cell adaptation and glucose homeostasis. *Cell Rep.* 2017; 18(13): 3192-3203. Doi: 10.1016/j.celrep.2017.03.005.
97. Cui C., Leander D. C., Gray S. M., El K., Chen A., Grimsrud P. A. α cells use both PCI/3 and PC2 to process proglucagon peptides and control insulin secretion. *Sci. Adv.* 2025; 11(38): DOI: 10.1126/sciadv.ady8048.
98. Taszczych D., Czernicka A., Taszczych K. Targeting GABA signaling in type I diabetes and its complications-an update on the state of the art. *Pharmacol. Repts.* 2025; 77: 409-424. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s43440-025-00697-7>.
99. Ferrannini E., Camastra S., Gastaldelli A., Maria Sironi A., Natali A. B-cell function in obesity: effects of weight loss. *Diabet.* 2004; 53(S3): S26-33.
100. Campola F., Pofi R., Venneri M. A., Isodori A. M. Priming metabolism with the type -5 phosphodiesterase: The role of cGMP hydrolyzing enzymes. *Curr. Op. Pharmacol.* 2021; 60: 298-305.
101. Ashmore T., Roberts L. D., Morash A. J., Kotwica A. O., Fnnerty J. Nitrate enhances skeletal muscle fatty acid oxidation via a nitric oxide-mediated mechanism. *BMC Biol.* 2015; 13 (art ID. 110).
102. Panasenko A., Sinitsky A., Sinitsky M., Khutornaya M., Barbarash O. The role of polymorphism in the endothelial homeostasis and vitamin D metabolism genes in the severity of coronary artery disease. *Biomed.* 2023; 11(9): 2382.
103. Choi Y. K., Kim Y-M. Regulation of endothelium and vascular function by carbon monoxide via crosstalk with nitric oxide. *Front. Cardiovasc. Med.* 2021; 649630.
104. Yang Y., Luo H., Cheng L-X., Liu K. Inhibitory role for GABA in atherosclerosis. *Med. Hypothes.* 2013; 81(5): 803-804.
105. Aggeletopoulou I., Tsiounis E. P., Triantos C. Vitamin D and metabolic dysfunction associated steatotic liver disease: novel mechanistic insights. *IJMS.* 2024; 25(9): 10.3390/ijms2509490.

106. Li Y., Tong C. H., Rowland C. M., Radcliff J., Bare L. A. Association of changes in lipid levels with changes in vitamin D levels in real-world setting. *Sci. Rep.* 2021; 11: 21536.
107. Garcia-Villafranca J., Guillen A., Castro J. Involvement of nitric oxide/CGMP signaling pathway in the regulation of fatty acid metabolism in rat hepatocytes. *Biochem. Pharmacol.* 2003; 65(5): 807-812.
108. Roumeguere T., Zouaoui- Boudjeltia K., Hauzeur C., Ramal A., Schulmanc C. Decrease ApoB/ApoA-I ratio and CVS risk; A tadalafil pleiotropic effect: Preliminary study on healthy volunteers. *Prog. Urol.* 2008; 18(13): 1087-91.
109. Koka S., Aluri H. S., Xi L., Lesnefsky E. J., Kukreja R. C. Chronic inhibition of PDE-5 with tadalafil attenuates mitochondrial dysfunction in type 2 diabetic hearts: Potential role of NO/SIRT1/PGC-1 α signalling. *Am. J. Physiol. Heart. Circ. Physio.* 2014; 306(11): H1558-1568.
110. Koka S., Kukreja R. Chronic inhibition of PDE-5 with tadalafil affords cardioprotection in a mouse model of metabolic syndrome: Role of nitric oxide. *Mol. Cell Biochem.* 2020; 468(1-2): 47-58.
111. Ginsberg H. N., Packard C., Aguilar-Salinas C., Aversa M., Ference B. A. Triglyceride-rich lipoproteins and their remnants; Metabolic insights, role in atherosclerosis cardiovascular diseases, and emerging therapeutic strategies-A consensus statement from the European Atherosclerosis Society. *Eur. H. J.* 2024; 42(47): 4791-4806.
112. Daviglius M.L., Ferdinand K. C., Loptz J. A. G., Wu X., Monsalvo M. L. Effects of evolocumab on low-density lipoprotein cholesterol, non-high density lipoprotein B, and lipoprotein (a) by race and ethnicity: A meta-analysis by individual participants data from double-blind and open label extension studies. *J. Am. Heart Assoc.* 2021; 10(1): e016839.
113. Dhiman P., Kumar R., Singh D. Neuronal nitric oxide synthase activation by tadalafil protects neurological impairments in a zebrafish larva model of hyperammonemia. *Lif. Sci.* 2025; 361: 123325.
114. Maneshi E., Cellai I., Aversa A., Mello T., Filippi S. Tadalafil reduces visceral adipose tissue accumulation by promoting preadipocyte's differentiation towards a metabolically healthy phenotype: Studies in rabbits. *Mol. Cell. Endocrinol.* 2016; 424(15): 50-70.

115. Prakash P., Manchandra P., Paouri E., Zhang C., Davalos D., Chopra G. Amyloid β induces lipid droplet-mediated microglia dysfunction via the enzyme diacyltryglycerol-O-acyl transferase 2 (DGAT2) in Alzheimer's disease. *Immun.* 2025; 58(6): 1536-1552.
116. Leyrolle Q., Laye S., Nadja A. Direct and indirect effects of lipids on microglia function. *Neusc. Lett.* 2019; 708: 134348.
117. Shi Y., Shi Y., Jie R., He J., Luo Z., Li J. Vitamin D: The crucial neuroprotective factor for nerves. *Neurosc.* 2024; 56(12): 272-285.
118. Zhu V. T. A., Hoang T. X., Kim J. Y. Vitamin D3 facilitates the M2 polarisation and β -amyloid uptake by human microglia. *Biomed Res. Int.* 2023; 10. 1155/2023/3483411.
119. Loving B. A., Bruce K. D. Lipid and lipoprotein metabolism in microglia. *Front. Physiol.* 2020; 11: 10. 3389/fphysiol.2020.00393.
120. Li Q., Zhao Y., Guo H., Li Q., Yan C. Impaired lipophagy induced-microglial lipid droplets accumulation contributes to the buildup of TREM1 in diabetes-associated cognitive impairment. *Autophag.* 2023; 19(10): 2639-2656. Doi: 10.1080/15548627.2023.2213984.
121. Xing J., McKenzie T., Hu J. Lipid-laden microglia: Characterization and roles in diseases. *Cells.* 2025; 14(16): 1281. <https://doi.org/10.3390/cells.14161281>
122. Behi T., Gupta R., Chigurupati S., Singh S., Sehgal A., Badavath V. N. Natural and synthetic agents targeting reactive carbonyl species against metabolic syndrome. *Mols.* 2022; 27(5): 10. 3390/molecules.27051583.
123. Andrade S., Nunes D., Dabur M., Ramalho M. J., Pereira M. C., Loureiro J. A. Therapeutic potential of natural compounds in neurodegenerative diseases: Insights from clinical trials. *Pharmaceut.* 2023; 15(1): 212. Doi: 10.3390/pharmaceutics15010212.
124. Sandoval-Salazar C., Oviedo-Solis C. I., Lozoya-Gloria E., Aguilar-Zavala H., Sotis-Ortiz M., Perez-Vazquez V. Strawberry intake ameliorates oxidative stress and decreases in GABA levels induced by high-fat diet in frontal cortex of rats. *Antiox. (Basel).* 2019; 8(3): 70.
125. Golmohammadi M., Meibodi S. A.A., Al-Hawary S.I.S., Gupta J., Sapaer I.B., Najm M. A. A. Neuroprotective effects of resveratrol on retinal ganglion cells in glaucoma in rodents: A narrative review. *An. Mod. Exp. Med.* 2024; 7(3): 195-207.
126. Joseph J. A., Shukitt-Hale B., Denissova N. A., Prior R.L. Cao G., Martin A. Long-term dietary strawberry, spinach or vitamin E supplementation retards the onset of age-related neuronal signal-transduction and cognitive behavioral deficits. *J. Neurosc.* 1998; 18(19): 8047-8055.

127. Vergroesen J. E., de Crom T. O. E., van Duijn C. M., Voortman T., Klaver C. C. W., Ramdas W. D. MIND diet lowers risk of open-angle glaucoma: The Rotterdam Study. *Eur. J. Nutri.* 2022; 62(1): 477-487.
128. Gasinuas K., Galgauskas S. Green tea-a new perspective of glaucoma prevention. *Int. J. Ophthalmol.* 2022; 15(5): 747-752.
129. Mihyaqui A., Castillo M. E. C., Cano A., Hernandez-Ruiz J. Comparative study of wild cvhamomile plants from the North-West of Morocco: Bioactive components and total antioxidant capacity. *J. Med. Plants Res.* 2021; 5(10): 431-441.
130. Savage K., Firth J., Stough C., Sarris J. GABA-modulating phyto-medicines for anxiety: A systematic review of preclinical and clinical evidence. *Phytother. Res.* 2017; 32(1): 3-18.
131. Schweiger S., Mathes F., Posey K., Kickstein E. Resveratrol induces dephosphorylation of tau by interfering with the MIDI-PP2A complex. *Sci. Rep.* 2017; 7: 13753.
132. Manchope . F., Calikto-Campos C., Coelho-Silva L., Zarpelon A. C., Pinho-Ribeiro F. A. Naringenin inhibits superoxide-anion-induced inflammatory pain: Role of oxidative, cytokines, Nrf2 and the NO-cGMP-PKG -K_{ATP} channel signaling pathway. *PLoS One.* 2016; 11(8): e0153015.
133. Salinaro A. T., Cornelius C., Koverech A., Lodato F., Muccili V. Cellular stress response, redox status and vitagenes in glaucoma: A system oxidant disorder linked to Alzheimer's disease. *Front. Pharmacol. Expt. Pharmacol. Drug Disc.*, 2014: 00129.
134. Ohara K., Inoue Y., Sumy Y., Morikawa M., Matsuda S. Oxidative stress and heart rate variability in patients with vertigo. *Acut. Med. Surg.* 2014; 2(3): 163-168.
135. Miao D., Golltzman D. Mechanisms of action of vitamin D in delaying aging and preventing disease by inhibiting oxidative stress. *Vits. Horm.* 2023; 121: 293-318. <https://doi.org/10.1016/bs.vh.2022.09.004>.
136. Loussouarn M., Krieger-Liszky A., Svilar L., Bily A., Birtic S., Havaux M. Carnosic acid and carnosol, two major antioxidants of rosemary, act through different mechanisms. *Plant Physiol.* 2017; 175(3): 1381-1394. Doi: 10.1104/pp.17.01183.
137. Zhang Y., Wang Y., Zhang X., Qin G., Zhang D. Inhibition of glutamatergic trigeminal nucleus caudalis vestibular nucleus projection neurons attenuates vestibular dysfunction in the chronic-NTG model of ,migraine. *J. Headach. Pain.* 2023; 24(1): 77. DOI: 10.1186/s10194-023-01607-z.

138. Ibitoye R. T., Castro P., Cooke J., Allum J., Arshad Q., Murdin L. A link between frontal white matter integrity and dizziness in cerebral small vessel disease. *NeuroImage: Clin.* 2022; 35: 103098.
139. Carpi-Santos R., Maggesissi R. S., von Seehausen M. P., Calaza K. C. Retinal exposure to high-glucose condition modifies the GABAergic system: Regulation of nitric oxide. *Expt. Eye Res.* 2017; 162: 116-125.
140. Calabrese V., Cornelius C., Mancuso C., Barone E., Calafato S. Vitagenes, dietary antioxidants and neuroprotection in neurodegenerative diseases. *Front. Biosc.* 2009; 14: 376-397.
141. Zhu Z., Shi Z., Xie C., Gong W., Hu Z., Peng Y. A novel mechanism of GABA protecting HUVECs against H₂O₂-induced oxidative stress. *Comp. Biochem. Physiol.* 2019; 217: 68-75.
142. Libonati G. A., Leone A., Martellucci S., Gallo A., Albrera R., Lucisano S. Prevention of recurrent BPPV: The role of combined supplementation with vitamin D and antioxidants. *Audiol. Res.* 2022; 12(14): 445-456.
143. Schur R. M., Gao S., Yu G., Chen Y., Maeda A., Palczewski K. New GABA modulators protect photoreceptor cells from light-induced degeneration in mouse models. *FASEB J.* 2018; 32(6): 3289-3300.
144. Telegina D. V., Antonenko A. K., Fursova A. Z., Kolosova N. C. The glutamate/GABA system in the retina of male rats: Effects of aging, neurodegeneration, and supplementation with melatonin and antioxidant SKQI. *Biogerontol.* 2022; 23(5): 571-585.
145. Zheng W., Zhao X., Wong J., Lu L. Retinal vascular leakage occurring in GABA Rho-I subunit deficient mice. *Expt. Eye Res.* 2010; 90(5): 634-640.
146. Kanduri S. Current understanding of age-related macular degeneration. *Int J. Ret.* 2020; 3(2): DOI:<https://doi.org/10.35479/ijretina.2020.vol11003.iss0>.
147. Wang M.Y., Yang J-M., Wu Y., Li H., Zhong Y-B. Curcumin -activated wtn5a pathway mediated Ca²⁺ channel opening to affect myoblast differentiation and skeletal muscle regeneration. *J. Cach. Sarcop. Musc.* 2024; 15(5): 1834-1849.
148. Rahimi M R, Faraji H, Ravosh S. The Effect of Strawberry Extract Supplementation on Caspase -3 and Cytochrome C After Resistance Exercise in Non-athletic Women. *J Kermanshah Univ Med Sci.*, 2023; 26(4): e126940. <https://doi.org/10.5812/jkums-126940>.

149. Yoon, Y.E.; Ju, S.H.; Kim, Y.; Lee, S.-J. Natural Flavonoids for the Prevention of Sarcopenia: Therapeutic Potential and Mechanisms. *Int. J. Mol. Sci.* 2025; 26: 7458. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijms26157458>.
150. Bang J. W., Parra C., Yu K., Wollstein G., Schuman J. S., Chan K. C. Gaba decrease is associated with degraded neural specificity in the visual cortex of glaucoma patients. *Comm. Biol.*, 2023; 6: 67.
151. Kumari K., Sharma G. S., Gupta A., Singh K. S., Singh L. R. Functionally active cross-linked protein oligomers formed by homocysteine thiolactone. *Sci. Rep.* 2023; 13: 5620.
152. Lee Y-A., Kang S-G., Song S-W., Kim S-H. Association between homocysteine and vitamin D levels in asymptomatic Korean adults. *Ntr.* 2024; 16(8): 1155.
153. Richerer S., Ulanski II L., Bhandari A., Popenko N.. Longevinex improves human atrophic AMD photoreceptor/retinal pigment epithelium mediated dark adaptation. *J. Adv. Med. Medic. Res.* 2017; 21 (10): 1-19. <https://doi.org/10.9734/BMJMR/2017/33820>.
154. Holden J. M., Wareham L.K. CGMP signaling: a potential therapeutic target of neurodegeneration in glaucoma. *Neural. Regen. Res.* 2022; 18(6): 1267-1268
155. Fang W., Yu J., Wei J., Jiang C., Huang X. Activation of the GABA-alpha receptor by berberine rescues retinal ganglion cell to attenuate experimental diabetic retinopathy. *Front. Mol. Neurobiol.* 2022; 15 <https://doi.org/10.3389/fnmol.2022.930599>.
156. Baran D. T. Nongenomic actions of the steroid hormone I-alpha, 25-dihydroxyvitamin D3. *J. Cell Biochem.*1994; 56(3): 303-6.
157. Bhattarai P., Bhattarai J. P., Kim M. S., Han S. K. Non-genomic action of vitamin D3 on NMDA and kainite receptor mediated actions in juvenile gonadotrophin-releasing hormone neurons. *Reprod. Fertil. Develop.* 2016; 29(6): 1231-1238.
158. Iorio R., Celenza G., Petricca S. Multi-target effects of β -caryophyllene and carnosic acid at the crossroads of mitochondrial dysfunction and neurodegeneration: From oxidative stress to microglia-mediated neuroinflammation. *Antioxd.* 2022; 11(6): 1199. <https://doi.org/10.3390/antiox11061199>.
159. Bartik L., Whitfield G. K., Kacmarska M., Lawmiller C. L., Moffet E.W. Curcumin: A novel nutritionally derived ligand of the VDR with implication for colon cancer chemoprevention. *J. Nutr. Biochem.* 2010; 21(12): 1153-1161.
160. Liu Y-M., Fan H-R., Ding J., Huang C., Deng S. Curcumol allosterically modulates GABA(A) receptors in a manner distinct from benzodiazepines. *Sci. Rep.* 2017; 7: 46654.

161. Moghaddam S. N., Qujeq D., Efahani A. S.R. Effect of curcumin on the hypothalamus levels of the potent inhibitory neurotransmission , GABA. 2015; 3(1): 24-27.
162. Li K-X., Wang Z-C., Machuki J. O. A., Li M-Z., Wu Y-J. Benefits of curcumin in the vasculature: A therapeutic candidate for vascular remodelling in arterial hypertension and PAH. *Front. Physiol* 2022; 13-2022.
163. Kruangtip O., Chootip K., Temkitthawon P., Changwicht K., Chuprajob T. Curcumin analogues inhibit PDE-5 and dilates rat pulmonary arteries. *J. Pharm. Pharmacol.* 2015; 67(1): 87-95.
164. Koka S., Das A., Salloum F. N., Krukeja R. C. PDE-5 inhibitor tadalafil attenuates oxidative stress and protects against myocardial ischemia-reperfusion injury in T2D mice. *Free Rad. Biol. Med.* 2013; 60: 80-88.
165. Law G., Nathoo N. A., Reiner E., Berkowitz J., Warner S. T. Correlation between glaucoma and erectile dysfunction. *J. Glauc.* 2016; 25(9-7): 6-9.
166. He W., Liu J., Liu D., Hu J., Jiang Y. Alterations in the PDE-5 pathway and oxidative stress correlate with erectile dysfunction in spontaneously hypertensive rats. *J. Cell. Mol. Med.* 2020; 24(24): 14280-14292.
167. Wang S., Teschemacher A. G., Paton J. F. R., Kasparov S. Mechanism of nitric oxide action on inhibitory GABAergic signalling within the nucleus tractus solitarii. *FASEB J.* 2006; 20(9): 1537-1539.
168. Maddox J. W., Gleason E. Nitric oxide promotes GABA release by activating a voltage-independent Ca^{2+} influx pathway in retinal amacrine cells. *J. Neurophysiol.* 2017; 117(3): 1185-1199.
169. Zhu Y., Moksha L., Salowe R., Vrathasha V., Pham K., Lee R. Integrating neuroprotection, antioxidative effects, and precision medicine in glaucoma management with bioactive compounds. *Biomed. Pharmacother.* 2025; 190: 118319.
170. Kim K. T., Chung K. J., Lee H. S., Ko I. G., Kim C. Neuroprotective effects of tadalafil on gerbil dopaminergic neurons following cerebral ischaemia. *Neural. Regen. Res.* 2013; 8(8): 693-701.
171. Yang C., Zhu Q., Chen Y., Ji K., Li S., Wu Q. Review of the protective mechanisms of curcumin on cardiovascular disease. 2024; Dove press <https://doi.org/10.2147/DDDT.S445555>.

172. Gul A., Pastuszak A., Kabasakal L., Bates J., Altinay S. Tadalafil preserves penile nitric oxide synthase from detrimental effects of paroxetine in rats. *Euras. J. Med.* 2019; 51(1): 60-63.
173. Musicki B., Bivalacqua T. S., Champion H. S., Burnett A. L. Sildenafil promotes eNOS activation and inhibits NADPH oxidase in the transgenic sickle cell mouse penis. *J. Sex. Med.* 2015; 11(2): 424-430.
174. Yaguas K., Bautista R., Quiroz Y., Ferrebuz A., Pons H., Franco M. . Chronic sildenafil treatment corrects endothelial dysfunction and improves hypertension. *Am. J. Nephrol.* 2010; 31: 283-91.
175. Ebrahimi F., Shafaroodi H., Asadi S., Nezami B. G., Ghasemi M., Rahimpour P. Sildenafil decreased cardiac cell apoptosis in diabetic mice: Reduction of oxidative stress as a possible mechanism. *Can. J. Physiol. Pharmacol.* 2009; 87: 556-64.
176. Oudot A., Behr-Roussel D., Le Coz O., Poirier S., Bernabe J., Alexandre L. How does chronic sildenafil prevent vascular oxidative stress in insulin-resistant rats? *J. Sex. Med.* 2010; 7(1): 79-88.
177. Koka S., Aluri H. S., Xi L., Lesnefsky E. J., Kukreja R. C. Chronic inhibition of PDE-5 with tadalafil attenuates mitochondrial dysfunction in type 2 diabetic hearts: Potential role of NO/SIRT1/PGC-1 α signalling. *Am. J. Physiol. Heart. Circ. Physio.* 2014; 306(11): H1558-1568.
178. Khoshakhlagh P., Bahrololouma-Shjapourabadi M., Mohammadiradi A., Ashtarat-Nakhai L., Minate B., ,Minaie B. Beneficial effect of PDE-5 inhibitors in experimental inflammatory bowel disease: Molecular evidence for involvement of oxidative stress. *Toxicol. Mechan. Methods.* 2006; 17(5): 281-288.
179. Zhang L., Seo J. H., Li H., Nam G., Yang H. O. The PDE-5 inhibitor, KJH-1002, reverses a mouse model of amnesia by activating a cGMP-cAMP response element binding protein pathway and decreasing oxidative stress. *BJP.* 2018; 175(16): 3347-3360.
180. Oriaifo S. E. O., Adegboro B., Oriaifo D. O., Oriaifo A. Non-sustainable environments and unhealthy lifestyles amplify the dyshomeostasis of immunomodulation in infectious diseases and ageing. *WJPPS.* 2023; 12(9): 178-273.
181. Hung M., Birmingham W. C., Ocampo M., Mohajeri A. The role of vitamin D in cardiovascular diseases. *Nutrients.* 2023; 15(16): 3547.
182. Caban M., Owczarek K., Lewandowska U. The role of MMPs and their tissue inhibitors on ocular diseases: Focusing on potential mechanisms. *IJMS.* 2022; 23(8): 4256. Doi: 10.3390/ijms23084256

183. Wareham L. K., Dordea A. C., Schleifer G., Yao V., Balten A (Increased bioavailability of cGMP prevents retinal ganglion cell degeneration. *Neurobiol. Dis.*, 2019; 121: 65-75.
184. Layana A. G., Minnella A. M., Garhofer G., Aslana T., Holz F. Vitamin D and age-related macular degeneration. *Nutrients*. 2017; 9(10): 1120.
185. Quayyam S., Muhammad T., Slominski R. M., Hassan M. I., Tuckey R. C. Vitamin D and lumisterol novel metabolites can inhibit SARS-CoV2 replication machinery enzymes. *Ajp. Endocrin. Metab.* 2021: 00174.
186. Rolf L., Damoiseaux J., Hutinga I., Kimenal D., van den Ouweland J. Stress-axis regulation by vitamin D in multiple sclerosis. *Front. Neurol.* 2018; 9: 263.
187. Daryabor G., Gholijan N., Kahmini F. R. A review of the critical role of vitamin D axis on the immune system. *Expt. Mol. Pathol.* 2023; 132-133 2023: 104866.
188. Rolando M., Barabino S. Dry eye disease: What is the role of vitamin D? *IJMS*. 2023; 24(2): 1458.
189. Sharif N. A. Destruction of retinal-brain components and connections in glaucoma: Disease causation and treatment options for eyesight preservation. *Cuu. Res. Neurobiol.* 2022; 3: 100037.
190. Boltz A., Schmidl D., Weigert G., Lasita M., Pemp B. Effect of latanoprost on choroidal blood flow in healthy subjects. *Invest. Ophthalmol. Vis. Sci.* 2011; 52(70): 4410-5. Doi: 10.1167/iovs.11-7263
191. Capece M., Montorio D., Comune C., Aveta A., Melchionni A., Celentano G. Retinal and optic disc vascular changes in patients using long-term tadalafil; A prospective non-randomized matched-pair study. *Diagn. (Basel)*. 2021; 11(5); 802. DOI: 10.3390/diagnostics11050802.
192. Kremmer S, Manoiu R, Smok C, Klee S, Anastassiou G, Link D, Stodtmeister R. Tadalafil zur Senkung des retinalen Venendruckes – ein neuer Ansatz in der Therapie des primären Offenwinkelglaukoms? [Tadalafil to lower retinal venous pressure-a new approach to treatment of primary open-angle glaucoma?]. *Ophthalmologie*. 2023; 20(10): 1045-1048. German. doi: 10.1007/s00347-023-01813-9.
193. Ozer M. A., Ozen S., Polat N., Ogreden E., Demirelli E. Effects of tadalafil on macular parameters and choroidal thickness in diabetic patients. *J. Ret-Vitr.* 2018; 27: 156-161.
194. Tang X., Jaenisch R., Sur M. The role of GABAergic signalling in neurodevelopmental disorders. *Nat. Rev. Neurosci.* 2021; 22(5): 290-307.

195. Kirmse K., Zhong C. Principles of GABAergic signaling in developing cortical network dynamics. *Cell Rep.* 2022; 38(3): 110568.
196. Deida G., Bazarth I., Cancedda L. Modulation of GABAergic transmission in developmental and neurodevelopmental disorders: Investigating physiology and pathology to gain therapeutic perspectives. *Front. Cell. Neurosci.* 2014; 8: 2014.00119.
197. Wu X, Wei J, Yi Y, Gong Q, Gao J. Activation of Nrf2 signaling: A key molecular mechanism of protection against cardiovascular diseases by natural products. *Front Pharmacol.* 2022 Dec 8; 13: 1057918. doi: 10.3389/fphar.2022.1057918.
198. Fenercioglu AK. The Anti-Inflammatory Roles of Vitamin D for Improving Human Health. *Curr Issues Mol Biol.* 2024; 46(12): 13514-13525. doi: 10.3390/cimb46120807.
199. Alam C., Aufreiter S., Georgiou C. J., Hoque M. T., Finnel R. H., O'Connor D. L. Upregulation of reduced folate carrier by vitamin D enhances brain folate uptake in mice lacking folate receptor alpha. *PNAS USA.* 2019; 116(35): 17531-17540. doi: 10.1073/pnas.2101687118.
200. Bobrowski-Khoury N., Ramaekers V. T., Sequeira J. M., Quadros E. Folate receptor alpha autoantibodies in autism spectrum disorders: Diagnostics, treatment and prevention. *J. Pers. Med.*, 2021; 11(8): 710. doi: 10.3390/jpm.11080710.
201. Laman J. D., Huizinga G-J., Jacobs B. C. Guillain-Barre syndrome: Expanding the concept of molecular mimicry. *Trends Immunol.* 2022; 43(4): 296-308.
202. Qin X-Y., Ha S-Y., Chen L., Zhang T., Li M-Q. Recent advances in folates and autoantibodies against folate receptor in early pregnancy and miscarriage. *Nutrien.* 2023; 15(23): 4882.
203. Mashayekhi P., Handipour E., Shabani S., Salehi Z. Folate receptor alpha autoantibodies in the serum of patients with relapsing-remitting multiple sclerosis (RRMS). *Clin. Neurol. Neurosurg.* 2024; 237: 108161.
204. Srivastava V. K., Khattar D., Shukla A., Bhanarkar U. Systematic review: Role of vitamin D3 in immune system regulation. *Eur. J. Cardiovasc. Med.* 2025; 15(3): 102-109.
205. Ullah H. Gut-vitamin D interplay: Mitigating immunosenescence and promoting healthy ageing. *Immunol. Age.* 2025; 22(20). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12979-025-00574-y>.
206. Ramaekers V. T., Quadros E. V. Cerebral folate deficiency: Early diagnosis, intervention and treatment strategies. *Nutrien.* 2022; 14(15): 3096. doi:10.3390/nu14153096.

207. Cerchiali N., Mancuso M., Navari E., Giannini N., Casani A. P. Aging with cerebral small disease and dizziness: The importance of undiagnosed vestibular disorders. *Front Neurosc.* 2017; 8: 241. doi: 10.3389/fneur.2017.00241.
208. Yang C., Zhu Q., Chen Y., Ji K., Li S., Wu Q. Review of the protective mechanisms of curcumin on cardiovascular disease. 2024; Dove press <https://doi.org/10.2147/DDDT.S445555>.
209. Singh A., Bennell G., de Prey J., Buchwald N., Eskander R. Small vessel disease of the brain. *Cardiol. Res. Pract. AHJ Plus.* 2023; 27: 100277.
210. Kim J-S., Newman-Toker D. E., Kerber K. A., Jahn K., Bertholon P., Waterston J. E. Consensus document of the committee for the classification of vestibular disorders of the Barany Society. 2022; 32(3): 205-222.
211. Su C., Yang X., Wei X., Zhao R. Association of cerebral small diseases with gait and balance disorders. *Front. Ag. Neurosc.* 2022; 14: 834496.
212. Smith E. E., Markus H. S. New treatment approaches to modify the course of cerebral small vessel diseases. *Stroke.* 2019; 51(1): 119: 024150.
213. Muneeb M., Mansou S. M., Saleh S., Mohammed R. A. Vitamin D and rosuvastatin alleviate T2D-induced cognitive dysfunction by modulating neuroinflammation and canonical/noncanonical Wnt/ β -catenin signaling. *PLOS One.* 2022; 17(11): e0277457.
214. Bath P. M., Wardlaw J. Pharmacological treatments and prevention of cerebral small vessel disease : A review of potential interventions. *Int. J. Stroke.* 2015; 10(4): 469-78.
215. Liao F. F., Lin G., Chen X., Zheng W., Raghov R. Endothelial nitric oxide deficient mice: A model of spontaneous cerebral small vessel disease. *Am. J. Pathol.* 2021; 191(11): 1932-1945.
216. Sun K., Liu H. Emerging biomarkers and frontier therapies unveiling the role of endothelial dysfunction in cerebral small vessel disease (CSVD). *Front. Neurosc.* 2025; 16: 2025: 1615883.
217. Baldelli P., Hernandez G. J. M., Carabelli V., Carbone E. BDNF enhances GABA release probability and non-uniform distribution of N and P/Q -type channels on release sites of hippocampal inhibitory neurons. *J. Neurosc.* 2005; 25(13): 3358-3369.
218. Marek M., Cichori N., Saluk-Bijak J., Bijak M., Miller E. The role of vitamin D in stroke prevention and the effects of its supplementation for post-stroke rehabilitation: A narrative review. *Nutr.* 2022; 14(13): 2761.
219. Siotto M., Santoro M., Aprile I. Vitamin D and rehabilitation after stroke: State of art. *J. Appl. Sci.* 2020; 10(6): 1061973.

220. Fiore M., Terracina S., Ferraguti G. Brain neutrophins and plant polyphenols: A powerful connection. *Mols.* 2025; 30(12): 2657.
221. Mazzanti G., Giacomo S. D. Curcumin and resveratrol in the management of cognitive disorders: What is the clinical evidence? *Mols.* 2016; 21(9): 1243.
222. McQuail J. A., Frazier C. J., Bizon J. L. Molecular aspects of age-related cognitive decline: The role of GABA signaling. *Trend. Mol. Med.* 2015; 21(7): 450-460.
223. Lahwani P., Polk T., Garrett D. D. Modulation of brain signal variability in visual cortex reflects aging, GABA, and behavior. *eLif.* 2025; E83865. Doi: 10.7554/eLife.83865.
224. Lalwani P., Garret D. D., Polk T. A. Dynamin recovery: GABA agonists restores neural variability in older, poor performing adults. *J. Neurosc.* 2021; 41(45): 9350-9360.
225. Pauls M. M. H., Fish J., Binnie L. R., Benjamin P., Betteridge S., Clarke B. Testing the cognitive effects of tadalafil. Neuropsychological secondary outcomes from the PASTIS trial. *Cereb. Circ. -Cogn. Behav.* 20234; <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cccb.2023.100187> NCT00123456.
226. Urios A., Ordone F., Garcia-Garcia R., Mangas-Losada A., Leone P., Gallego J. J. Tadalafil treatment improves inflammation, cognitive function, and mismatch negativity of patients with low urinary tract symptoms and erectile dysfunction. *Sci. Rep.* 2019; 9:17119. DOI: 10.1038/s41598-019-53136-y.
227. Yu J., Gatton-Celli M., Zhu H., Bhat N. R., Sambamurti K. Vitamin D3-enriched diet correlates with a decrease of amyloid plaques in the brain of A β PP transgenic mice. *J. Alzh. Dis.* 2011; 25(2): 295-307.
228. Patel P., Shah J. Role of vitamin D in amyloid clearance via LRP-I upregulation in Alzheimer's disease: A potential therapeutic target? *J. Chem. Neuroanat.* 2017; 85: 36-42.
229. Tropea M. S., Gulisano W., Vacanti V., Arancio O., Puzzo D. Nitric oxide cGMP/CREB pathway and amyloid -beta crosstalk: From physiology to Alzheimer's disease. *Free. Rad. Biol. Med.* 2022; 193(2): 657-668.
230. Hamstra S. I., Roy B. D., Tisdu P., MacNeil A. J., Klentrou P. Beyond its psychiatric use: The benefits of low-dose lithium supplementation. *Curr. Neuropharmacol.* 2023; 21(4): 891-910.
231. Jamhiri M., Safari F., Ghalenaei J.A./., Mehrjerdi F.Z., Eslami M. Resveratrol alleviates cognitive impairment in chronic cerebral hypoperfusion by targeting LINGO-I, NgRI, p75, and RhoA/ROCK-2 pathways. *Iran J. Phar. Res.*, 2025; 24(1): e158864.

232. Pirmoradi Z., Nakhare M., Ranjibar H., Kalentar-Neyestanalti D., Kohlmeier K. A. Resveratrol and vitamin D3 decrease Lingo-I levels, and improve behavior in harmaline-induced essential tremor, suggesting potential therapeutic benefits. *Sci. Reps.* 2024; 14: 0864.
233. Aurelian J., Zamfirescu A., Nedelescu M., Stolescu S., Gita C. D. Vitamin D impact on stress and cognitive decline in older Romanian adults. *Farmacia.* 2024; 72(6): <https://doi.org/10.31925/farmacia.2024.6.7>.
234. Chien W-L., Liang K-C., Teng C-M., Kuo S-C., Lee F-Y. Enhancement of learning behavior by a potent nitric oxide- guanylate cyclase activator YC-I. *Eur. J. Neurosci.* 2005; 21: 1679-1688.
235. Bollen E., Akkerman S., Puzzo D., Gulisano W., Palmeri A. Object memory enhancement by combining sub-efficacious doses of specific PDE-I. *Neuropharmacol.* 2015; 95: 361-366.
236. Bollen E., Puzzo D., Rutten K., Privitera L., De Vry J. Improved long-term memory via enhancing cGMP-PKG signalling requires cAMP-PKA signalling. *Neuropharmacol.* 2014; 391(11): 2505.
237. Mayne P. E., Burne T. H. J. Vitamin D in synaptic plasticity, cognitive function, and neuropsychiatric illness. *Trend. Neurosc.* 2019; 42(4): 293-306.
238. Rihali V., Khan H., Kaur A., Singh T. G., Abdel-Daim M. M. Therapeutic and mechanistic intervention of vitamin D in neuropsychiatric disorders. *Psychiatr. Res.,* 2022; 317: 114782.
239. An L., Shen Y., Chopp M., Zacharek A., Venkat P., Chen Z. Deficiency of eNOS exacerbates brain damage and cognitive deficit in a mouse model of vascular dementia. *Agi. Dis.,* 2021; 12(3): 732-745. <https://doi.org/10.143361.AD.2020.9523>.
240. Staab J. P., Ruckenstein M. J. Expanding the differential diagnosis of chronic dizziness. *Arch. Otolaryngol. Head Neck Surg.,* 2007; 133(2): 170-176. Doi: 10.1001/archotol.133.2.170.
241. Hesse R., Lausser L., Gummert P., Schmid F., Wahler A. Reduced cGMP level in CSF of Alzheimer's disease patients correlate with severity of dementia and concurrent depression. *Alzh. Res. Ther.,* 2017; 9: 17. Doi: 10.1186/s13195-017-0245-y.
242. Fujimori S., Yoneda Y. Neuropsychiatric disease and GABA. *Nihon Shinkei Seishin Yakurigaku Zasshi.* 2004; 24(5): 265-71.

243. Balasubramanian A., Kunchala K., Shahbaza A., Kar A., Sankar J. Association of vitamin D deficiency as an independent risk factor for myocardial infarction and its therapeutic implications: A systematic review. *Cureus J. Med. Sci. Cureus*: 2025; 77375.
244. Separham A., Sohrabi B., Pourafkari L., Sepasi N., Ghaffari S. Vitamin D is a predictor of ST segment resolution and infarct size following thrombolysis in patients with acute ST elevation myocardial infarction. *Turk. Kardiyol. Dem Ars.* 2017; 45(4): 324-332.
245. Liang D., Zhou L., Zhou H. Gabaergic system in atrioventricular node pacemaker cells controls electrical conduction between the atria and ventricles. *Cell Res.* 2024; 34: 556-571.
246. Shi Y., Li Y., Yin J., Hu H., Xue M. A novel sympathetic neuronal Gabaergic signalling system regulates norepinephrine release to prevent ventricular arrhythmias after acute myocardial infarction. *Acta Physiol (Oxf)*. 2019; 227(2): e13315.
247. Gentile C., Kesteven S., Wu J., Bursill C., Davies M. Endothelial nitric oxide synthase plays a protective role against myocardial infarction. *Free Rad. Biol. Med.* 20189; 128(SI): S26.
248. Cortese-Krott M. M., Surorava T., Leo F., Heuser S. K., LoBue A. Red blood cell eNOS is cardioprotective in acute myocardial infarction. *Redox. Biol.* 2022: 102370.
249. AIRuwaili R., Al-Kuraishy H. M., Airuwaili M., Khalifa A. K., Alexiou A. The potential therapeutic effect of PDE-5 inhibitors in the acute ischaemic stroke. *Mol. Cell. Biochem.* 2024; 479: 1267-1278.
250. Kass D. A. Cardiac role of cyclic GMP hydrolyzing phosphodiesterase type 5: From experimental models to clinical trials. *Curr. Heart Fail. Reps.* 2012; 9(3): 192-199.
251. Severino P., D'Amato A., Mancone M., Palazzuoli A., Mariani M. V. Protection against ischaemic heart disease: A joint role for eNOS and the K_{ATP} channel. *IJMS*, 2023; 24(9): 24097927.
252. Qiu Y., Zhang X., Zhang Y., Bao W., XUE Y. Vitamin D attenuates airways inflammation and airway responsiveness in T2-low asthma by suppressing autophagy via the mTOR pathway. *Eur. Resp. J.* 2024; 64(S6): PA4843.
253. Hansdottir S., Monick M. M. Vitamin D effects on lung immunity and respiratory disease. *Vit. Horm.* 2011; 86: 217-237.
254. Gaudet M., Plesa M., Mogas A., Jaleddine N., Hamid Q. Recent advances in vitamin D implications in chronic lung diseases. *Resp. Res.*, 2022; 23: 252.

255. Gallos G., Townsend E., Yim P., Virag L. Airway epithelium is a predominant source of endogenous airway GABA and contributes to relaxation of airway smooth muscle tone. *Am. J. Physiol. Lung Cell Mol. Physiol.*, 2013; 304(3): L191-7.
256. Blanco E. E. A., Pinge M. C. M., Neto O. A. A., Pessoa N. G. Effects of nitric oxide in mucociliary transport. *Braz. J. Otorhinolaryn.* 2015; 75(6): 866-871.
257. Weatherald J., Hubert M. Keep them alive: The use of PDE-5 inhibitors in severe pulmonary hypertension associated with interstitial lung disease. *Respirol.* 2023; 28(3): 212-214.
258. Ritz Z., Salsman M. L., Young D. A., Lippert A. R., Khan D. A. Boosting nitric oxide in stress and respiratory infections: Potential relevance for asthma and COVID-19. *Br. Beh. Imm-Health.* 2021; 14: 100255.
259. Abdelaziz R. R., Elkashef W. F., Said E. Tadalafil reduces airway hyperreactivity and protects against lung and respiratory airways dysfunction in a rat model of silicosis. *Int. Immunopharmacol.* 2016; 40: 530-541.
260. Braga M., Simmons Z., Norris K. C., Ferrini M. G., Artaza J. N. Vitamin D induces myogenic differentiation in skeletal muscle derived stem cells. *Endocrinol. Connect.* 2017; 6(3).
261. Burno R., Vantagiata C., Pisa V., Azzoni E., Bassi M. Nitric oxide sustains long-term skeletal muscle regeneration by regulating fate of satellite cells via signalling pathways requiring Vangl2 cGMP. *Stem Cells.* 2011; 30(2): 197-209.
262. Latham C. M., Brightwell C. R., Keeble A. R., Thomas N. T., Fry C. S. . Vitamin D promotes skeletal muscle regeneration and mitochondrial health. *Front. Physiol.* 2021; 12: 2021.660498.
263. Lepper C., Partridge T. A., Fan C. M. An absolute requirement for Pax7-positive satellite cells in acute injury-induced skeletal muscle regeneration. *Develop.* 2011; 138(17): 3639-46.
264. Li W-R., Qin L-H., Poon C. C-W., Wong M-S., Feng R N. Vitamin D3/VDR signalling attenuates skeletal muscle atrophy by suppressing renin angiotensin system. *J. Bon. Min. Res.*, 2021; 37(1): 121-136.
265. Jin H., Oh E-J., Lee B-Y. GABA prevents age-related sarcopenic obesity in mice with high-fat-diet-induced obesity. *Cells.*, 2023; 12(17): 2146.
266. Miyashita K., Itoh H., Tsujimoto H., Tamura N., Fukunaga Y. Natriuretic peptides /cAMP-/cGMP- dependent protein kinase cascades promote muscle mitochondrial biogenesis and prevent obesity. *Diabet.*, 2009; 58(12): 2880-92.

267. Tan L., Cao Z., Chen H., Xie Y. Curcumin reduces apoptosis and promotes osteogenesis of human periodontal ligament stem cells under oxidative stress in vitro and in vivo. *Lif. Sci.*, 2021; 270: 119125.
268. Jin Z., Chang B., Wei Y., Yang Y., Zhang H. Curcumin exerts chondroprotective effects against osteoarthritis by promoting AMPK/PINK1/Parkin-mediated mitophagy. *Biomed. Pharmacother.*, 2022; 151: 113092.
269. Buhrmann C., Brockmueller A., Mueller A-L., Shayan P., Shakibaei M. Curcumin attenuates environmental-derived osteoarthritis by Sox/NF-kappa β signalling axis. *Int.J. Mol. Sci.*, 2021; 22(14): 7845.
270. Wang M.Y., Yang J-M., Wu Y., Li H., Zhong Y-B. Curcumin -activated wtn5a pathway mediated Ca²⁺ channel opening to affect myoblast differentiation and skeletal muscle regeneration. *J. Cach. Sarcop. Musc.* 2024; 15(5): 1834-1849.
271. Azouz A. A., Saleh E., Abo-Saif A. A. AlisKiren, tadalafil, and cinnamaidehyde alleviate join destruction biomarkers MMP3 and RANKL; in complete Freund's adjuvant arthritis model: Downregulation of IL6/JAK2/STAT3 signalling pathway. *Saudi Pharmaceut. J.*, 2020; 28(9): 1101-1111.
272. Huyut Z., Alp H. H., Bakan N., Yildirim S., Sekoroglu M. Stimulating effect of vardenafil, tadalafil, and uedenafil on VEGF, angiogenesis, vitamin D3 , bone morphogenic protein in ovariectomised rats. *Arch. Physiol. Biochem.* 2020; 128(4): 1121-1127.
273. Kim S-M., Taneja C., Perez-Pena H., Ryu V., Gumerova A. Repurposing erectile dysfunction drugs tadalafil and vardenafil to increase bone mass. *PNAS-USA.* 2020; 117(25): 14386-14394.
274. Yuasa K., Uehara S., Nagahama M., Tsuji A. Transcriptional regulation of cGMP-dependent protein kinase II (cCK-II) in chondrocytes. *Biosc. Biotechnol. Biochem.* 2010; 74(1): 44-9.
275. Miyazawa T., Ogawa Y., Chusho H., Yusoda A., Tamura N. cGMP -dependent protein kinase II plays a critical role in C-type natriuretic peptide-mediated endochondral ossification. *Endocrinol.* 2002; 143(9): 3604-9.
276. Sanghi D., Mishra A., Sharma A. C., Singh A., Natu S. M. Does vitamin D improve osteoarthritis of the knee?: A randomised controlled trial. *Clin. Orthop. Relat. Res.* 2013; 471(11); 3556-3562.

277. Szychlinska M. A., Imbesi R., Castrogiovanni P., Guglielmino C., Ravalli S. Association of vitamin D supplementation on articular cartilage morphology in a young healthy sedentary rat model. *Nutr.* 2019; 11(6): 1260.
278. Voisin T., Joannes A., Marzadec C., Lagadfic-Gossmann D., Naoures C. Antifibrotic effects of vitamin D3 in human lung fibroblasts derived from patients with idiopathic pulmonary fibrosis. *J. Nutr. Biochem.* 2024; 125: 109558.
279. Mansour H. M., Salama A. A. A., Abdel-Salam R. M., Ahmed N. A. The anti-inflammatory and anti-fibrotic effects of tadalafil in thioacetamide-induced liver fibrosis in rats. *Can. J. Physiol. Pharmacol.* 2018; 90(12): 1308-1317.
280. Wu H., Chiou J. Potential benefits of probiotics and prebiotics for coronary heart disease and stroke. *Nutr.* 2021; 13(8): 2878.
281. Amin U., Jiang R., Raza S. M., Fan M., Liang L. Gut-joint axis: Oral probiotic ameliorates osteoarthritis. *J. Trad. Compl. Med.* 2022; 14(1): 26-39.
282. Du Z., Chen H., Cai Y., Zhou Z. Pharmacological use of GABA derivatives in osteoarthritis pain management: A systematic review. *BMC Rheumatol.* 2022; 6: 28.
283. Rodriguez-Archilla A., Mohamed-El-Founti N. Association of periodontitis with vitamin D and calcium levels: A meta-analysis. *Iberoam J. Med.* 2023; 5(1): 36-45.
284. Lima L., Gasper S., Rocha B. S., Alves R., Almeida M. G. Current clinical framework on nitric oxide role in periodontal disease and blood pressure. *Clin. Oral Investig.* 2024; 28(10): 521.
285. Braga J. D., Thongngam M., Kumrungsee T. Gamma-aminobutyric acid as a potential postbiotic mediator in the gut-brain axis. *Npi Sci. Food.* 2024; 8(16): 00253-2.
286. Wyatt M., Choudhury A., Von Dohlen G., Helleson J. L., Forsse J. S. Randomized controlled trial of moderate dose vitamin D alters microbiota stability and metabolite networks in healthy adults. *Microbiol. Spectr.* 2024; <https://doi.org/10.1128/spectrum.00083-24>.
287. Jain A., Madkan S., Patil P. The role of gut microbiota in neurodegenerative diseases. Current insights and their implications. *Cureus.* 2023; 15(1): e47861.
288. Zhu W., Gregory J. C., Org E., Buffa J. A., Gupta N. Gut microbiota metabolite TMAO enhances platelet hyperreactivity and thrombosis risk. *Cell.* 2016; 165(1): 111-129.
289. Mastrangelo A., Robles-Vera I., Galan M., Femenia-Muina M., Redondo-Urzaizqui A. Imidazole propionate is a driver and therapeutic target in atherosclerosis. *Nat.*, 2025; 09263.

290. Ameth B. Gut-brain axis and brain microbiome interactions from a medical perspective. *Brain Sci.*, 2025; 15(2). <https://doi.org/10.3390/brainsci15020167>.
291. Fang H., Anhe F., Zada D. K., Bana N. G., Rodrigues-Lacarda R. Gut substrate trap of D-lactate from microbiota improves blood glucose and fatty liver disease in obese. *Cell Metab.*, 2025: 07001.
292. Moon Y., Balke J. E., Madorma D., Siegel M. P., Knowels G. Nitric oxide regulates skeletal muscle fatigue, fibre type, and microtubule organization and mitochondrial ATP synthesis efficiency through cGMP-dependent mechanisms. *Antioxid. Redox. Signal.* 2017; 26(17): 966-985.
293. Aversa A., Fittipaldi S., Francomano D., Bimonte V. M., Greco E. A. Tadalafil improves lean mass and endothelial function in nonobese men with mild ED/LUTS: in vivo and in vitro characterization. *Endo.* 2020; .DOI.10.1007/S/2020-016-1208-4.
294. Arcangelis V., de Angelis L., Barbagallo F., Campolo F., de Oliveira do Rego A. G. Phosphodiesterase-5a signalling in skeletal muscle pathophysiology. *IJMS.* 2022; 24(1): 240703.
295. Sun E., Zhu X., Ness R., Murff H. J., Sun S., Yu C. Magnesium treatment increases gut microbiome synthesizing vitamin D and inhibiting CRC: Results from a double-blind precision-based randomized placebo-controlled trial. *Nutri.* 2025; <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ajcnut.2025>.
296. Yamazaki K., Kamada N. Exploring the oral-gut linkage: Interrelationship between oral and systemic diseases. *Mucosal Immunol.* 2023; 17(1): 147-153. Doi: 10.1016/j.mucimm.2023.11.006.
297. Fujiki H., Sueoka E., Rawangkan A. Human cancer stem cell are a target for cancer prevention using (-)-epigallocatechin gallate. *J. Canc. Res. Clin. Oncol.* 2017; 143: 2401-2412.
298. Zhao y., Cai L-L., Wang H-L., Shi X-J., Ye H-M. 1,25-dihydroxyvitamin D3 affects gastric cancer progression by repressing BMP promoter methylation. *Onco Targ. Ther.*, 2019; 12: 2343-2353.
299. Li W., Wang O-L., Liu X., Dong S-H., Li H-X. Combined use of vitamin D3 and metformin exhibits synergistic chemopreventive effects on colorectal neoplasm in rats and mice. *Can. Prev. Res.* 2014; 8(2): 139-148.
300. So J. Y., Suh N. Targeting cancer stem cells in solid tumors by vitamin D. *J, Steroid Biochem. Mol. Biol.*, 2015; 148: 79-85.

301. Jiang S., Qiu Y., Wang Z., Ji Y., Zhang X., Yan X. Carnosic acid induces antiproliferation and anti-metastatic property of esophageal cancer cells via MAPK signaling pathways. *J. Oncol.*, 2021; 4451533. Doi 10.1155/2021/4451533.
302. Wibowo S., Pramadhani A., Subandiyah S., Poeranto S., Handono K. Vitamin D3 induces stem cell activation via Lgr5-BMiI expression and improving mouse colitis histology index. *Narra. J.* 2023; 3(3): e430.
303. Chen L., Smanta A., Zhao L., Dudley N. R., Buehler T. Vitamin D3 induces mesenchymal-to-endothelial transition and promotes a proangiogenic niche through IGF-I signalling. *iScience.* 2021; 24(4): 102272.
304. Uthaiyah C. A., Beeraka N. M., Rajakshan R., Ramya C. M., Madhunapantula S. V. Role of neural stem cells and vitamin D receptor (VDR)-mediated cellular signalling in the mitigation of neurological diseases. *Mol. Neurobiol.* 2022; 59(7): 4065-4105.
305. Battacharya D., Gawali V. S., Kallag L., Toukam D., Koehler A. Therapeutically leveraging GABA_A receptors in cancer. *Expt. Biol. Med (Maywood).* 2021; 246(19): 2128.
306. Schuller H. M., Al-Wadei H. A. N., Majidi N. The GABA_B receptor is a novel drug target for pancreatic cancer. *Canc.* 2008; 112(4): 767-778.
307. Hickok J. R., Thomas D.D. Nitric oxide and cancer therapy: The Emperor has NO clothes. *Curr. Pharmacol. Des.* 2010; 16(4): 381-391.
308. Bian K., Sotolongo A., Lam H., Xiao H., Zhang D. NO-cGMP signalling and cancer therapy. *BMC Pharmacol. Toxicol.* 2013; 14(SI): 9. doi: 10.1186/2050-6511-14-SI-P9
309. Mujoo K., Sharin V. G., Martin E., Choi B-K., Sloan C. Role of sGC -cGMP signalling in tumor cell proliferation. *Nitric Ox.* 2009; 22(1): 43-50.
310. Acosta L. H., Pino M. T. L., Rocco M. V., Cabrilla J. P. sGC beta I subunit targets epithelial-to-mesenchymal transition and downregulates Akt pathway in endometrial and cervical cancer cells. *Heliyon.* 2024; 10(1): e23977.
311. Zhang L., Troccoli C. I., Mateo-Victoriano B., Lincheta L. M., Jackson E. Stimulating SGC with the clinical agonist riociguat restores the development and progression of castration-resistant prostate cancer. *Transl. Can. Biol. (Can Res).* 2025; 85(1): 134-153.
312. Pantziarka P., Sukhatme V., Crispino S., Bouche G., Meheus L. Repurposing drugs in oncology (ReDO)-selective PDE-5 inhibitors as anti-cancer agents. *Ecancer.* 2018; 12824.

313. Shen Y., Zhao P., Dong K., et al. Tadalafil increases the antitumor activity of 5-FU through inhibiting PRMT5 mediated glycolysis and cell proliferation in colorectal cancer. *Can. Metab.*, 2022: 00299-4
314. Borojevic A., Jaukovic A., Kukulj T., Mojsilovic S., Obradovic H., Trivanovic D. Vitamin D3 stimulates proliferation capacity, expression of pluripotency markers, and osteogenesis of human bone marrow mesenchymal stromal/stem cells, partly through SIRT1 signaling. *Biomol.* 2022; 12(2): 323. [Doi: 10.3390/biom12020323](https://doi.org/10.3390/biom12020323).
315. Hou Y. C., Lu C. L., Zheng C. M., Liu W. C., Yen T. H. The role of vitamin D in modulating mesenchymal stem cells and endothelial progenitor cells for vascular calcification. *IJMS.* 2020; 21(7): 2466. Doi: 10.3390/ijms21072466.
316. Shirazi H. A., Rasouli J., Ciric B., Rostami A., Zhang G-X. Vitamin D3 enhances neural stem cell proliferation and oligodendrocyte differentiation. *Exp. Mol. Pathol.* 2015; 98(2): 240-245.
317. Matakchione G., Gurau F., Silvestrini A. Anti-SASP and anti-inflammatory activity of resveratrol, curcumin and β -caryophyllene association on human endothelial and monocytic cells. *Biogerontol.* 2021; 22: 297-313.
318. Kreienkamp R., Croke M., Neumann M. A., Bedia-Diaz G., Graziano S., Dusso A. Vitamin D receptor signaling improves HGPS cellular phenotypes. *Oncotarg.* 2016; 7(21): doi: 10.18632/oncotarget.9065.
319. Ashapkin V. V., Kutueva L. I., Kurchashova S. Y., Kiree I. I. Are there common mechanisms between the HGPS and natural aging? *Front. Genetic. Agi.* 2019; 10: <https://doi.org/10.3389/fgene.2019.00455>.
320. Bittmann S., Alieva M. E., Villalon G., Bittmann L. The role of klotho in pediatric premature aging diseases. *Am. J. Biomed. Sci. Res.* 2023; 19(3): doi:10.34297/AJBSR.2023.19.002592.
321. Chen L., Yang R., Qiao W., Zhang W., Chen J. Dihydroxyvitamin D exerts an antiaging role by activation of Nrf2-antioxidant signalling and inactivation of p16/p53-senescence signalling. *Agin. Cell.* 2019; 18(3): e12957.
322. Wei Y., Li Z., Lai H., Lu P., Zhang B., Song L. Instant coffee is negatively associated with telomere length: Finding from observational and mendelian randomization analyses of UK biobank. *Nutr.* 2023; 15(6): 134. Doi: 10.3390/nu.15061354.
323. Russo C., Valle M. S., D'Angeli F., Surdo S., Malaguarnera L. Resveratrol and vitamin D: Eclectic molecules promoting mitochondrial health in sarcopenia. *IJMS.* 2024; 25(14): 7503.

324. Meex R. R. C., Blaak E. E., van Loon L. J. C. Lipotoxicity plays a key role in the development of both insulin resistance and muscle atrophy in patients with T2D. *Obes. Rev.*, 2019; 20(9): 1205-1217.
325. Fantini C., Corinaldesi C., Lenzi A., Migliaccio S., Crescioli C. Vitamin D as a shield against aging. *Int. J. Mol. Sci.*, 2023; 24(5): 5446.
326. Chen L. Dong Y., Bhagatwala J., Raed A., Huang Y., Zhu H. Effects of vitamin D3 supplementation on epigenetic aging in overweight and obese African Americans with suboptimal vitamin D status: A randomized clinical trial. *J. Gerontol. A. Biol. Sci. Med. Sci.*, 2019; 74(1): 91-98. Doi 10.1093/Gerona/gly223.
327. Cuyppers K., Maes C., Suinnen S. P. Aging and GABA. *Aging (Albany NY)*. 2018; 10(6): 1180-1187.
328. Yilmaz Y. Green tea mitigates the hallmarks of aging and age-related multisystem deterioration. *J. Agin. Dis.*, 2025; DOI: 10. 14336/AD 2025.0398.
329. Kumazawa Y., Watanabe K., Nagaoka I. The potential use of vitamin D3 and phytochemicals for their anti-aging effect. *Int. J. Mol. Sci.*, 2024; 25(4): 2125.
330. Golshiri K., Ataei-Fernandez E. C., Danser A. H. J., Roks A. J. M. The importance of the nitric oxide -cGMP pathway in age-related cardiovascular disease: Focus on PDE-I and soluble guanylyl cyclase. *Bas. Clin. Pharmacol. Toxicol.* 2019; 127(2): 67-80.
331. Danimayostu A. A., Martien R., Lukitaningsih E., Danarti R. Vitamin D3 and the molecular pathway of skin aging. *Ind. J. Pharm.*, 2023. DOI:10:22146/IJp.4929.
332. Ambagaspitiya S. S., Appuhamillage G. A., Wimalawansa S. J. Impact of vitamin D on skin aging, and age-related dermatologic condition. *Front. Biosc (Landmark Ed.)*. 2025; 30(1): 25463.
333. Al-Amin M.M., Hasan S.M.N., Alam T., Hasan A. T., Hossain I. Tadalafil enhances working memory and reduces hippocampal oxidative stress in both young and aged mice. *Eur. J. Pharmacol.* 2014; 745: 84-90.
334. Hayashi K., Sasaki H., Mugita T., Tomiyama T., Koizumi S. Effect of long-term administration of tadalafil on arteriolosclerosis: A prospective cohort study. *The J. Sex. Med.* 2022; 19(5-2): S211.
335. Ruffenach G., Homg J., Vallencourt M. Pulmonary hypertension secondary to pulmonary fibrosis: Clinical data, histopathology and molecular insights. *Respir. Res.*, 2020; 21: 303.

336. Haussler M. R., Haussler C. A., Whitfield G. K., Hsieh J-C., Thompson P.D. The nuclear vitamin D receptor controls the expression of genes encoding factors which feed 'the fountain of youth' to mediate healthful aging. *Mol. Biol.* 2010; 121(1-2): 88-97.
337. McNally P., Coughlan C., Bergsson G., Doyle M., Taggart C. Vitamin receptor agonists inhibit pro-inflammatory cytokine production from the respiratory epithelium in cystic fibrosis. *J. Cyst. Fibros.* 2011; 10(6): 428-34.
338. Schinner E., Wetzl V., Schramm A., Kees F., Sandner P. Inhibition of the TGF- β signalling pathway by cGMP -dependent kinase I in renal fibrosis. *FEBS Op. Biol.* 2017; 7(4): 550-561.
339. Sandner P., Stasch J. P. Antifibrotic effects of sGC stimulation and activators: A review of the preclinical evidence. *Resp. Med.* 2017; 122(1): 51-59.
340. Kawasaki K, Fushimi T, Nakamura J, Ota N. Guava leaf extract suppresses osteoarthritis progression in a rat anterior cruciate ligament transection model. *Food Sci. Nutr.* 2018; 6(4): 800-805. doi: 10.1002/fsn3.601.
341. Baerjee A., Farci P. Fibrosis and hepatocarcinogenesis: Role of gene-environment interactions in liver disease prognosis. *IJMS.* 2024; 25(16): 8641.
342. Adão R, Barreira B, Paternoster E, Morales-Cano D, Olivencia MA, Quintana-Villamandos B, Rodríguez-Chiaradía DA, Cogolludo A, Perez-Vizcaino F. Vitamin D as an add-on therapy to phosphodiesterase-5 inhibitor in experimental pulmonary arterial hypertension. *Am J Physiol Lung Cell Mol Physiol.* 2025; 328(2): L253-L259. doi: 10.1152/ajplung.00319.2024.
343. Lo S., Cao Z-B. Interplay between vitamin D and adipose tissue: Implications for adipogenesis and adipose tissue function. *Nutr.* 2023; 15(22): DOI:10.3390/nu15223832.
344. Pu Y., Zhang A., Wang P., Zhao Y., Li O. Dietary curcumin ameliorates aging-related cerebrovascular dysfunction through AMPK/UCP2 pathway. *Curr. Physiol. Biochem.,* 2013; 32(5): 1167-1173.
345. Suto K., Kamaru T., Arima T., Jardson C., Yanaka N., Kumrungsee T. Dietary GABA and its combination with vigabatrin mimic calorie restriction and induce obesity-like effects in lean mice. *J. Funct. Food.* 2021; 78: 104367.
346. Salehpour A, Hosseinpanah F, Shidfar F, Vafa M, Razaghi M, Dehghani S, Hoshiarrad A, Gohari M. A 12-week double-blind randomized clinical trial of vitamin D₃ supplementation on body fat mass in healthy overweight and obese women. *Nutr J.* 2012; 11: 78. doi: 10.1186/1475-2891-11-78.

347. Groeneweg G., Huygen F. G. P., Zijlstra F. J., Wesseldijk F., Bussman J. B. J. Effect of tadalafil on blood flow, pain, and function in chronic cold Complex Regional Pain Syndrome, a randomised controlled trial. *BMC Musculoskelet. Disord.* 2008; 9. Art. Ident.: 143.
348. Azari, H.; George, M.; Albracht-Schulte, K. Gut Microbiota–microRNA Interactions and Obesity Pathophysiology: A Systematic Review of Integrated Studies. *Int. J. Mol. Sci.*, 2024; 25: 12836. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijms252312836>.
349. Morris A. Link between the gut and adipose tissue. *Nat. Rev. Endocrinol.* 2017; 13: 501. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nrendo.2017.92>.
350. Virtue A. T., McCright S. J., Wright J. M., Jimenez M. T., Mowel W. K. The gut microbiota regulates white adipose tissue inflammation and obesity via a family of microRNAs. *Sci. Transl. Med.*, 2020; 11(496): eaa07892.